

AMBIENT-6G

Towards standardized 6G connectivity for ambient-powered energy neutral IoT devices

Deliverable D5.1

Use cases, KPIs and KVIs

Co-funded by
the European Union

AMBIENT-6G project has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101192113.

Date of delivery: 30th Aug, 2025

Version: 1.1

Project reference: 101192113

Call: HORIZON-JU-SNS-2024

Start date of the project: 1st Jan, 2025

Duration: 36 months

Document properties

Document Number:	D5.1
Document Title:	Use cases, KPIs and KVIIs
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Contractual Date of Delivery:	31 st Aug, 2025
Dissemination level:	PU
Status:	Final Version
Revision:	1.1
Filename:	AMBIENT-6G_5.1_v1.1

Revision History

Revision	Date	Issued by	Description
v0.1	17/03/2025	TEL	Baseline draft for the deliverable.
v0.2	24/03/2025	TEL	Merge contributions to Use Cases.
v0.3	12/05/2025	TEL	Inputs in Introduction, Technical Description, Use Case SotA and Conclusions.
v0.4	26/05/2025	TEL	Internal review.
v0.5	24/06/2025	TEL	External review.
v1.0	01/08/2025	TEL	Final version.
v1.1	11/11/2025	TEL	Reviewed final version (authors list updated).

Abstract

This deliverable describes relevant use cases in different vertical areas where energy-neutral device operation can bring particular benefits in terms of ease of use and maintenance, cost, and ecological footprint.

Keywords

AMBIENT-6G, Ambient-IoT, Energy-Neutral Devices, Use Cases, Key Performance Indicators, Key Value Indicators.

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Executive Summary

This document constitutes the issue of Deliverable D5.1: 'Use cases, KPIs and KVIs', within the framework of the project titled "AMBIENT-6G – Towards standardized 6G connectivity for ambiently-powered energy-neutral IoT devices" (Project Acronym: AMBIENT-6G; Grant Agreement No: 101192113).

This document presents a comprehensive analysis of the potential of Ambient Internet of Things (A-IoT) in enabling innovative and sustainable use cases, aiming at supporting future developments and standardization efforts within the European context. It is structured into five chapters, each addressing a key aspect of the topic.

- **Chapter 1** introduces the motivation behind the work, outlines the main objectives, and presents the structure of the document.
- **Chapter 2** provides a technical overview of A-IoT and the core technologies it builds upon, offering a conceptual foundation for the rest of the document.
- **Chapter 3** reviews the current state of the art in defining use cases for A-IoT, focusing on international standardization bodies and relevant European projects, both completed and ongoing.
- **Chapter 4** presents the proposed A-IoT use cases in detail. Each use case includes an analysis of functional requirements, key performance indicators (KPIs), and key value indicators (KVIs), covering environmental, social, economic, and innovation-related impacts.
- **Chapter 5** summarizes the main conclusions drawn from the work described in the document.

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Glossary

3GPP 3rd Generation Partnership Project.

4G fourth-generation.

5G fifth-generation.

6G sixth-generation.

ADC analog-to-digital converter.

AI artificial intelligence.

A-IoT Ambient Internet of Things.

AOA angle-of-arrival.

AP access point.

BLE Bluetooth low energy.

BS base station.

CDMA code division-multiple access.

CJT coherent joint transmission.

CN core network.

CO continuous operation.

COTS commercial off-the-shelf.

CRC cyclic redundancy check.

CSI channel state information.

D-MIMO distributed MIMO.

DB duty-cycled barebone.

DLI direct link interference.

DP duty-cycled persistent.

DPPM dynamic power path management.

DTLS Datagram Transport Layer Security.

EMF Electromagnetic Field.

eNB Evolved Node B.

END energy-neutral device.

EoL end of life.

ESL electronic shelf label.

ET Energy Transmitter.

ETSI European Telecommunications Standards Institute.

FCC Federal Communications Commission.

FEC forward error correction.

FFT fast Fourier transform.

GDPR General Data Protection Regulation.

GNSS global navigation satellite system.

GPS Global Positioning System.

HF high frequency.

IC integrated circuit.

IEEE Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers.

IMU inertial measurement unit.

IoT Internet of Things.

ISAC Integrated Sensing and Communication.

ISM industrial, scientific and medical.

KPI key performance indicator.

KVI key value indicator.

LCA life cycle assessment.

LCD liquid crystal display.

LED Light Emitting Diode.

LoRa long range.

LoRaWAN long-range wide-area network.

LoS line-of-sight.

LPWAN low-power wide-area network.

LTE Long Term Evolution.

M&O management and orchestration.

MAC Medium Access Control.

MCU microcontroller unit.

MEMS micro-electromechanical system.

MIMO multiple-input multiple-output.

ML machine learning.

NB-IoT narrowband IoT.

NFC near-field communication.

NOMA non-orthogonal multiple access.

OBU on-board unit.

OFDM orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing.

OLoS obstructed-line-of-sight.

OT Operational Technology.

OTA over-the-air.

OTA-TinyML Over-the-air TinyML.

PHY physical.

PMIC power management integrated circuit.

POS point-of-sale.

QoE Quality-of-Experience.

QoS quality-of-service.

QR quick response.

RAM random-access memory.

RBAC Role-Based Access Control.

RF radio frequency.

RFID radio frequency identification.

RIS reflective intelligent surface.

ROI return of investment.

RSS received signal strength.

RSSI received signal strength indicator.

RTI reusable transport item.

rUC representative Use Cases.

SDO Standard Development Organization.

SLAM simultaneous localization and mapping.

SNR signal-to-noise ratio.

TCO total cost of ownership.

TDMA time division-multiple access.

TENG Triboelectric Nanogenerator.

TinyML Tiny Machine Learning.

TLS Transport Layer Security.

ToF time-of-flight.

TR Technical Report.

TS Technical Specification.

UE user equipment.

UHF ultra-high frequency.

UID unique identifier.

UP ultra-pasive.

UV unmanned vehicle.

UWB Ultra-Wideband.

Wi-Fi Wireless Fidelity.

WLAN wireless local area network.

WPT wireless power transfer.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Ambient Internet of Things (A-IoT) is gaining importance due to the growing need for Internet of Things (IoT) networks that overcome the limitations of conventional battery-powered devices. Examples of these limitations are frequent maintenance, finite lifetime, or environmental concerns related to battery disposal and e-waste. A-IoT consists of wireless IoT networks fully or partially composed of ambient-powered energy-neutral devices (ENDs). ENDs rely on harvesting energy from different energy sources to function with reduced or no onboard storage, enabling deployment with net zero energy operation over time. Some typical examples of energy harvesting techniques are photovoltaic cells, piezoelectric generators, thermoelectric converters, or radio frequency (RF) scavenging. Moreover, ENDs can also be powered using RF signals generated and transmitted specifically for the purpose of feeding them. This is one of the possible ways to implement wireless power transfer (WPT).

The AMBIENT-6G project aims to design, prototype, validate, and standardise both hardware and software solutions for intelligent ENDs and the sixth-generation (6G) network infrastructure that connects them to the Internet. In this context, the definition and analysis of use cases is an important task. The identification of scenarios where A-IoT will be beneficial allows to ensure that innovations developed in AMBIENT-6G meet real world requirements, driving adoption of the solutions across consumers and industries.

1.2 Scope and Objectives

In this document, we address the work defined under AMBIENT-6G's Task **T5.1: Use case inventory and selection, requirements, KPIs and KVIs**. Task T5.1 aims to compile candidate use cases for A-IoT and analyse their functional requirements, key performance indicators (KPIs) and key value indicators (KVIs). Existing inventories and requirements from past and active initiatives are used as references, adapting them to A-IoT and 6G connectivity. With task T5.1, AMBIENT-6G lays the foundations for validation, benchmarking, and eventual industrial adoption of A-IoT solutions.

1.3 Structure of the Document

This document is organised into five chapters that provide a structured analysis of A-IoT and its potential applications.

Chapter 1 introduces the motivation for the study, outlines its primary objectives, and presents the structure of the document. Chapter 2 performs a technical overview of A-IoT, describing its enabling technologies and establishing a foundation for the next chapters. Chapter 3 examines the current state of the art in A-IoT use cases definition both in Standard Development Organizations (SDOs) and relevant European initiatives. Chapter 4 describes the proposed use cases in AMBIENT-6G. This analysis includes functional requirements; KPIs; and environmental, social, economic and innovation KVIs. Finally, Chapter 5 summarizes the main conclusions drawn from the work presented throughout the document.

Chapter 2

Ambient Internet of Things: Technical Description

The following chapter introduces the fundamental concepts of A-IoT to provide readers with a clear understanding of its principles and potential, serving as a foundation for the analysis of use cases presented in this deliverable.

This chapter covers the core principles and typical architectures of both active and passive ENDS. It then explores key technological challenges such as the trade-off between costs and functionality, energy harvesting, storage and management mechanisms, requirements in terms of connectivity and infrastructure, and security considerations. Finally, the chapter introduces the role of artificial intelligence (AI)/machine learning (ML) in enhancing the capabilities of A-IoT networks, laying the foundations for the analysis of relevant use cases in the next chapters.

2.1 Holistic Energy Neutral Device architecture

The development of a comprehensive END architecture is driven by the growing demands of contemporary digital ecosystems, particularly within the realms of the IoT and edge computing. These environments are defined by widespread deployments of interconnected devices that operate continuously and autonomously.

The vision of AMBIENT-6G on this holistic END architecture is summarized in Figure 2.1. Two different types of ENDS are considered: active devices and passive devices. The main difference between the two types of ENDS is the capability of active devices to generate their own RF carrier signals and, therefore, the ability to autonomously start uplink communications. In exchange for this higher performance, active ENDS are typically more complex and have a higher energy consumption than passive devices. Despite this difference, both types of devices also share many similarities, such as energy harvesting and energy buffer blocks, which are used to obtain power from sources like RF signals, solar energy, vibrations or temperature gradient, and distribute it among the rest of the blocks. Another important similarity is the lack of batteries to store energy, which are replaced by supercapacitors, small batteries or directly removed. More information can be found in AMBIENT-6G's deliverable **D2.1: END Architecture, Technology Trade-Off and Characterization** [1].

Figure 2.1: Device architecture of both active and passive ENDS [1].

2.1.1 Encompassing Performance vs. Cost vs. Material Usage Trade-off

Given the scale and operational requirements of such systems, reliance on conventional batteries or wired power sources is becoming increasingly impractical due to logistical challenges, environmental concerns, and economic limitations. To address these issues, a novel END architecture must optimise the trade-offs between **performance, cost, and material use**.

Advances in integrated circuits (ICs) and the development of miniature sensors and actuators enabled by micro-electromechanical systems (MEMSs) technology have significantly expanded the potential to design compact and cost-effective IoT nodes. Despite their small form factor, the ecological footprint of such electronic devices is substantially larger than their physical size suggests [2]. Contemporary IoT node architectures typically emphasize high hardware integration and often employ fully sealed enclosures to optimize size and provide mechanical protection. However, this design philosophy poses challenges for ecological sustainability, as it impedes disassembly, reuse, and recycling at the device's end-of-life.

A holistic END architecture offers a pathway to address these limitations by considering the full lifecycle of material use—encompassing design and production, operational use, and end-of-life processing. During the design and production phase, a critical consideration is whether the indirect ecological benefits of the device (e.g., energy savings during use) outweigh hypothetical environmental costs incurred from raw material extraction to manufacturing ("cradle-to-gate"). If this balance is favourable, the architecture should incorporate advanced energy storage, harvesting, and management circuits, alongside ultra-low-power wireless communication technologies such as backscatter and wake-up radio, to enable sustainable and economically viable system operation.

Extending the operational lifetime of IoT nodes is among the most impactful strategies to improve their ecological value. Batteries are often the primary limiting factor in device longevity. Therefore, minimising energy consumption and leveraging energy harvesting techniques are essential to prolong functional lifetimes and reduce the overall carbon footprint.

At the end-of-life stage, the prevailing "fire-and-forget" mindset contributes significantly to the global e-waste crisis. Since 2014, e-waste generation has increased by 9.2 million metric tons—a 21% rise. In 2019 alone, the fate of 82.6% (44.3 Mt) of generated e-waste remained untracked, raising serious environmental concerns [3]. In response, research into biodegradable electronics has gained momentum over the past two decades [4], [5]. While there remains a considerable performance gap between biodegradable materials and state-of-the-art silicon-based electronics, promising developments have emerged in areas such as energy harvesting and sensing. For example, biodegradable photovoltaic materials, though less efficient than conventional alternatives, offer competitive advantages in terms of reduced production costs,

lower environmental impact, and minimal waste generation [4].

To support sustainability, future IoT device designs should adopt principles of repairability, reusability, and recyclability. A modular design approach can facilitate the upgrading, replacement, or recycling of individual components as they become obsolete or fail. However, it is important to note that modularity may not always represent the most sustainable solution, as it often introduces additional material overhead.

2.1.2 Circuits for Energy Storage, Harvesting, and Management

An essential component of the architecture of an ambient-powered device is the integration of self-sustaining power systems capable of operating autonomously without the need for frequent battery replacements. END systems rely on a combination of low-power circuit design, energy harvesting from ambient sources, efficient energy storage, and intelligent power management [6].

For energy storage, small-scale batteries such as thin-film lithium and solid-state microbatteries are commonly used due to their relatively high energy density and compatibility with compact form factors. Recent advancements include flexible and biodegradable battery designs tailored for wearable and environmental applications. However, such batteries face challenges including aging, leakage current, and limited charge-discharge cycles. Complementary to batteries, ultracapacitors or supercapacitors offer high power density and rapid charge and discharge capabilities. These characteristics make them well-suited for devices with pulsed power profiles, such as those that transmit data intermittently. Hybrid energy storage systems that combine batteries and supercapacitors are increasingly deployed to optimize energy delivery and extend operational lifetime.

Energy harvesting plays a central role in enabling A-IoT nodes to be self-powered. Devices can combine multiple energy sources to increase reliability and ensure continuous operation under varying environmental conditions. Common sources include photovoltaic cells that harvest light, both indoor and outdoor, thermoelectric generators that exploit temperature gradients, piezoelectric materials that capture mechanical vibrations [7], and RF energy harvesting that taps into ambient radio waves from Wireless Fidelity (Wi-Fi), cellular networks, etc. Multi-source designs [8] support concurrent operation or intelligent switching between sources depending on energy availability, usage demands, and environmental conditions.

Equally important is the efficient management of harvested and stored energy. Power management integrated circuits (PMICs) are designed for ultra-low power operation, often with quiescent currents in the nano-ampere range. These circuits include energy harvesters capable of cold-starting from very low voltages, and dynamically regulate energy flow through buck, boost, or switched-capacitor converters. Power path management strategies, such as dynamic power path management (DPPM), allow for simultaneous energy storage and device operation, maintaining system uptime and efficiency. Regulation circuits, including low-dropout regulators and high-efficiency converters, condition the energy for use by analog and digital subsystems. Real-time power monitoring is essential, enabling measurement of both harvested energy and power consumption. This data supports energy-aware operation, where sensing, processing, and communication schedules adapt based on the available energy budget.

These advancements collectively enable ambient-powered devices to operate reliably in diverse and dynamic environments with minimal human intervention. As energy harvesting and storage

technologies continue to evolve, they will play a pivotal role in the widespread deployment of sustainable and autonomous A-IoT systems.

2.1.3 Enabling Energy Neutral Device Connectivity

Ambient-powered ENDs suffer from intermittently turning off due to insufficient power for communication and operation of the radio and microcontroller unit (MCU). The inconsistency of the energy harvesting is the major challenge, as ENDs cannot rely on a stable harvesting rate to predict if they have enough power to perform a communication cycle. The most challenging is the support of active ENDs that can generate the signal on their own instead of communicating using back-scattering. Feasibility of different connectivity protocols have been studied in literature: long-range wide-area network (LoRaWAN) [9]–[11], Bluetooth low energy (BLE) [12]–[14] narrowband IoT (NB-IoT): [15]–[17].

In 6G, active ENDs are supposed to function similar to legacy IoT devices with a significantly lower complexity [18]. Legacy IoT devices in cellular networks operate according to NB-IoT standard. The major part of the energy consumption of NB-IoT devices is spent on channel access. The default channel access mechanism for these devices after returning from the sleep state is random channel access, when a random preamble from a predefined set is sent to request a grant. However, to enable low-latency critical IoT applications, two other channel access mechanisms has been introduced: grant-free and fast uplink grant, also known as configured grant. When grant-free access is used, devices are allowed to transmit data in randomly selected resources without negotiation with the base station. Therefore, the latency is significantly reduced, but under an expense of a higher chance of unsuccessful transmissions due to collisions. Fast uplink grant allows the base station to provide grants to the associated devices in advance, before data packets appear in their queues. The efficiency of this mechanism significantly depends on how accurately the base station predicts the activity of devices. For ENDs, the selection of the channel access mechanism is especially important, as different mechanisms require different energy consumption at different network conditions. Studies [16], [17] compare the performance of these mechanisms in terms of outage probability and energy consumption for ambient powered ENDs. Both studies reveal a high potential for the fast uplink grant scheme, especially for predictable traffic patterns.

2.1.4 Secure Low-power Protocol Design

ENDs have an extremely low energy budget and thus are typically resource constrained, making them less suited to implementing traditional security mechanisms [19]. Due to limited processing power, memory, and energy availability, adding complex cryptographic protocols has been challenging. Since communication typically accounts for the largest share of power consumption in IoT devices [20], security solutions that increase communication overhead or require extensive computation are typically viewed as impractical or too costly for such nodes.

This perspective especially applies to security frameworks that involve frequent or continuous connections with other devices or cloud infrastructures. Protocols like Transport Layer Security (TLS) and Datagram Transport Layer Security (DTLS), while providing strong security guarantees in traditional IoT or Internet systems, tend to impose significant computational and communication overhead that is unusable for ultra-low-power systems [21]. The handshakes,

key exchanges and multiple message exchanges involved can quickly drain the limited energy budgets of ENDS.

To overcome these limitations, research has been shifted toward lightweight cryptographic protocols and efficient key management schemes designed specifically for constrained devices. In the context of low-power wide-area networks (LPWANs) — such as LoRaWAN, NB-IoT, and Sigfox — security is typically integrated at the network and application layers with a strong emphasis on minimizing energy consumption [22]. For example, LoRaWAN employs symmetric AES-128 encryption for both network authentication and payload confidentiality, relying on pre-distributed keys and a lightweight joint procedure. NB-IoT, as part of the Long Term Evolution (LTE)/fifth-generation (5G) family, inherits the robust authentication and encryption features of the cellular stack while tailoring its signaling and power behavior for IoT scenarios. Sigfox, despite its ultra-narrowband and highly constrained message format, supports optional payload encryption and sequence-based replay protection mechanisms. These protocols exemplify how security can be designed to coexist with strict energy budgets — limiting handshake complexity, minimizing message exchanges, and relying on pre-shared or efficiently negotiated keys. Although such mechanisms may not match the flexibility or end-to-end guarantees of traditional Internet-grade protocols like TLS, they represent a balance between security and energy efficiency for ENDS.

In addition to protocol-level approaches, there is growing interest in physical (PHY) layer security techniques, especially for backscatter and energy-harvesting devices. PHY security leverages the inherent characteristics of the wireless medium - such as channel randomness or hardware-specific imperfections (e.g., radio frequency fingerprints) - to enable lightweight authentication and key generation without relying on heavy cryptographic computations. These techniques are particularly attractive for ultra-low-power and intermittently powered devices, as they can reduce or even eliminate the need for energy-expensive message exchanges [23]. Although current implementations face challenges related to environmental variability and device stability, recent research has shown encouraging progress in improving the reliability and robustness of PHY-layer security mechanisms [24], [25].

2.1.5 Infrastructure Enablers for Wireless Power Transfer

RF-WPT is a promising solution for powering large-scale ENDS ecosystems, overcoming the limitations of traditional battery-powered ENDS in terms of maintenance, scalability, and environmental impact. It stands among WPT technologies for its ability to support simultaneous charging of multiple ENDS, enable mobility, and operate in non-line-of-sight conditions—albeit with some efficiency trade-offs. Unlike ambient energy harvesting systems, the performance of WPT-enabled networks is dictated by the end-to-end conversion efficiency—which encompasses the Energy Transmitter (ET), the wireless channel, and the RF energy harvesting circuits—safety regulations, and coverage. This is because the ETs provide a controllable contactless power delivery to sustain the long-term operation of ENDS.

Conveniently deploying multiple spatially distributed ETs is critical to eliminate blind spots in the network and distribute the energy according to the application requirements. Robotic WPT implementations with moving or flying ETs [26] bring significant advantages over traditional static ETs due to their ability to dynamically shorten the charging distance. Moreover, robotic WPT potentially reduces deployment costs as fewer ETs may be required to accomplish the same

task. More importantly, robotic WPT can cope more efficiently with temporal service requirements. Distributed ET infrastructures inherently have physically large apertures, which benefit WPT through (i) better regulatory compliance, (ii) higher WPT efficiency, (iii) inherent interference mitigation and channel hardening [27]. Coherent joint transmission (CJT) is an emerging paradigm for distributed multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) architectures, promising jointly phase-coherent downlink beamforming with spatially distributed ETs, but necessitates establishing tight temporal synchronization and phase calibration of ETs with distributed clocks [28], [29].

Energy beamforming plays a crucial role in enhancing end-to-end conversion efficiency without requiring an increase in the ETs' transmit power. Efforts to develop cost-effective beamforming solutions primarily focus on two key domains: system architecture and signal processing optimization. The former research direction focuses on direct modifications to the architecture of the ETs, whereas the latter focuses on minimizing the overhead of the signal processing algorithm.

Popular techniques in the architectural domain include the use of low-resolution analog-to-digital converters (ADCs) and simplifications to the analog front-end via antenna selection architectures, parasitic arrays, and even implementations without RF chains. Motivated by the idea of hybrid beamforming, recent efforts have focused on developing novel architectures that can efficiently handle numerous antennas with a limited number of RF chains. This includes lens antenna arrays [30], dynamic metasurface antennas [31], and reflective intelligent surface (RIS)-equipped ETs [32]. Other efforts, such as the development of movable antennas, have been directed to give the ETs sufficient flexibility to explore the channel in the quest for the best configuration that increases the harvested power and with a limited number of antennas. Another promising research direction that allows the use of energy-efficient low-resolution ADCs is direct link interference (DLI) mitigation in bistatic or multistatic ET infrastructures [33], [34].

From the signal processing perspective, the main challenge of energy beamforming lies in balancing computational efficiency with performance gains, necessitating innovative approaches to mitigate complexity. Notably, the benefits of accurate channel state information (CSI)-based strategies quickly vanish, and may even reverse, as the number of ENDS increases due to the energy-demanding training process. That is why alternative beamforming strategies have been proposed to rely on statistical CSI [35], received energy feedback [36], and the positions of the ENDS [37], which are easier to acquire and vary slowly.

2.2 Cloud-Edge Device Orchestration, Offloading and On-device Machine Learning

Cloud-edge device orchestration and offloading are critical for low-power A-IoT devices due to their inherent resource constraints, including limited computational power, memory, and energy supply. The traditional cloud-centric AI paradigm, which offloads all data processing to centralized servers, introduces significant latency, bandwidth limitations, and privacy concerns, making it unsuitable for real-time and sensitive A-IoT applications. However, by distributing intelligence closer to the device, at the edge, these limitations can be mitigated.

The primary importance of cloud-edge orchestration and offloading for A-IoT devices lies in enabling on-device and edge intelligence, which significantly improves response times by eliminating

the need for constant data transmission to the cloud. These transmissions are costly for ENDS. Local processing allows devices to analyse sensory inputs and execute actions instantaneously, fostering greater autonomy and efficiency. Furthermore, processing data at the device enhances privacy by reducing the exposure of sensitive information across networks. It also enables personalization, allowing devices to adapt continuously to user behaviours and preferences without requiring constant connectivity. Crucially, by reducing frequent data transmissions, device intelligence contributes to substantial energy efficiency, a vital factor for battery-operated IoT devices and essential for ENDS. However, the local processing comes at a cost of higher complexity and energy/resource consumption. Therefore, it is necessary to analyse whether these adverse effects are compensated by the benefits of local processing.

On-device ML for ENDS is a rapidly advancing field that enables intelligent data processing directly on ultra-low-power IoT nodes. These devices operate under severe constraints in terms of energy, memory, and compute capacity. To address these limitations, researchers have developed highly optimized ML models using techniques, such as quantization, pruning, and knowledge distillation, allowing inference to run on microcontrollers with as little as 32–256 KB of random-access memory (RAM). Two foundational tools in this space are TensorFlow Lite for Microcontrollers, which enables the deployment of compact ML models on bare-metal systems without an operating system [38] and CMSIS-NN, a library of highly optimised neural network kernels for ARM Cortex-M processors that significantly boosts inference efficiency on embedded hardware [39]. These frameworks are often used together to deliver real-time ML capabilities on devices with minimal energy budgets.

These capabilities are being applied across a wide range of use cases. In cooperative mobile robotics, ENDS equipped with on-device ML can perform local obstacle detection or gesture recognition, enabling real-time interaction without relying on continuous connectivity. In smart agriculture, devices can classify soil moisture levels or detect crop diseases using lightweight classifiers. Wearable medical sensors use on-device ML to detect anomalies in heart rate or motion patterns, while in smart logistics, ENDS monitor package conditions and predict equipment failures. Even in cultural heritage settings, such as museums, ambient powered tags with embedded ML could personalize visitor experiences by recognizing user behaviour or preferences. These applications benefit from the ability to process data locally, which reduces latency, preserves privacy, and minimizes energy consumption [40].

Recent research highlights the growing interest in enabling not just inference but also on-device learning. Techniques for continual learning and federated learning are being adapted to operate under the constraints of ENDS, allowing devices to personalize models without transmitting raw data. For example, the authors in [41] provide a comprehensive survey of on-device ML from an algorithmic and learning theory perspective, emphasizing the importance of resource-constrained learning. Meanwhile, newer work explores the feasibility of on-device training and adaptation in real-world systems [42]. As 6G and A-IoT ecosystems evolve, on-device ML is expected to become a foundational capability, enabling scalable, autonomous, and sustainable intelligence across sectors ranging from industrial automation and smart homes to healthcare and environmental monitoring.

On the other hand, there are some advantages to processing data at the edge. A primary benefit is that computationally intensive tasks can be shifted from local devices to more powerful edge servers or cloud infrastructure. Offloading from the device effectively overcomes inherent hardware limitations of the IoT devices, allowing them to participate in complex analytical tasks

and machine learning inferences that would otherwise be beyond their native processing capabilities, ultimately expanding their functional scope and enabling advanced functionalities like personalized services and intelligent automation.

Thus, there is a balance that must be achieved between local processing and offloading the task to the edge/cloud. Several techniques are employed to facilitate cloud-edge orchestration and offloading for low-power devices. Device Edge Offloading is a key strategy where computational tasks are offloaded from resource-constrained devices to more powerful edge servers. This allows complex machine learning inferences to be remotely executed in proximity to the devices, optimizing latency and network bandwidth, particularly for ENDS. Techniques such as model compression, federated learning, and resource-efficient energy-aware algorithms are crucial for overcoming hardware limitations and enabling Tiny Machine Learning (TinyML) on constrained devices. Energy-aware task scheduling is also vital, optimizing energy consumption by prioritizing essential tasks, dynamically allocating processes, and leveraging techniques like duty cycling to ensure reliable operation despite fluctuating power availability from ambient sources. Split learning and federated learning can be integrated to enhance performance and learning, addressing both personalization and generalization in edge AI environments. Over-the-air TinyML (OTA-TinyML) [43] is another method that enables remote updates, configuration, and execution of TinyML models, enhancing scalability and flexibility.

Despite the numerous advantages, several challenges hinder the full realization of cloud-edge device orchestration and offloading for low-power devices. Foremost among these are the inherent limitations of hardware resources, particularly for ENDS, and the energy availability. Training complex models on such devices remains impractical, necessitating advanced techniques like model compression and federated learning. Updating models dynamically on IoT devices is also a significant challenge, often requiring physical access or complex communication protocols. The intermittent power availability in battery-less environments can lead to disrupted inference and decreased model accuracy, despite the use of techniques like duty cycling and model quantization. Furthermore, deep learning models often demand substantial memory and computational resources, creating trade-offs between inference complexity and device longevity. While edge processing reduces cloud dependencies, maintaining model updates and adaptability can be challenging if connectivity is not consistently stable.

Chapter 3

Use Cases: State of the Art

The purpose of this chapter is to provide an overview of the state of the art on the use cases for A-IoT. As A-IoT continues to gain importance, identifying and analysing its potential applications has become a priority for both research and standardisation communities. This chapter presents the main efforts to define A-IoT use cases from two primary sources: international SDOs and publicly funded research and innovation projects. First, this chapter explores how organizations like 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) and the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) have contributed to shaping the A-IoT landscape by identifying key application and technical requirements. Second, it reviews relevant use cases proposed in European research projects, highlighting real-world deployments.

3.1 International Standardization Bodies

In recent years, standardization of A-IoT has gained momentum with several organizations recognizing its potential. 3GPP has taken a leading role in trying to integrate A-IoT into the 5G ecosystem. In addition to 3GPP, entities such as IEEE have also started working on A-IoT standardisation.

3GPP has recognized A-IoT as an IoT technology with the potential to enable large-scale connectivity with net zero energy consumption. The concept is based on the integration of ENDS into cellular and non-cellular networks, enabling ubiquitous connectivity in a number of applications.

In Release 18, 3GPP initiated preliminary studies on A-IoT as part of its efforts to enhance 5G. Release 18 laid the groundwork by exploring the potential applications of energy-harvesting IoT devices. The study item Technical Report (TR) 38.848 “Study on Ambient IoT (Internet of Things) in RAN” [44] addresses the feasibility of meeting design targets for relevant use cases of A-IoT. The study considered various aspects (including device types, communication methods, and network requirements) to support the operation of A-IoT devices in 5G. It also identified several use cases for A-IoT, emphasizing their applicability in scenarios where battery replacement is challenging. More specifically, two main use case groups were proposed. The first group, or Group A, is based on the deployment environment, and consists of three sub-categories: Indoor, Outdoor and Indoor/Outdoor. The second group, or group B, is based on the functionality/application of the use case, and it is formed by four subcategories: Inventory,

Sensing, Positioning and Command. By combining both groups, eight different categories are generated, which were called representative Use Cases (rUC) in TR 38.848 [44]. Table 3.1 defines these eight rUCs.

Table 3.1: Use cases defined in TR 38.848 [44].

rUC	Description
Indoor Inventory	Discover what goods are present in a specific area. A-IoT devices attached to these goods can report an identifier and additional info upon request from the network.
Outdoor Inventory	
Indoor Sensing	A-IoT devices are associated with a sensor. A-IoT devices send data obtained by the sensor triggered by different conditions (periodically, triggered by the network, when the A-IoT device is completely powered...).
Outdoor Sensing	
Indoor Positioning	Determine the location of certain goods. A-IoT devices attached to these goods report information like identification or location.
Outdoor Positioning	
Indoor Command	A-IoT device is associated with an actuator. Commands to control the actuator are usually sent by the network.
Outdoor Command	

In Release 19, 3GPP continued to develop the vision introduced in Release 18. While the term “Ambient IoT” is not always explicitly used, the use cases being discussed align closely with its principles: massive-scale deployment of low-cost, low-power devices with intermittent or passive connectivity to mobile networks. These use cases are being explored within several 3GPP working groups, most notably SA1 (Services) and SA2 (System Architecture).

In TR 22.840 "Study on Ambient power-enabled Internet of Things" [45], 3GPP presented a feasibility study on the potential support of A-IoT within 3GPP systems. This document represented the first formal effort within 3GPP to analyse the applicability of A-IoT to existing and future mobile network. The objective of TR 22.840 was to evaluate use cases that reflect realistic applications of A-IoT across multiple vertical domains, and to identify the technical requirements and limitations in current 3GPP specifications. The report focused on exploratory analysis to support future normative work.

In Technical Specification (TS) 22.369 "Service requirements for ambient power-enabled IoT" [46], which used the outcome from TR 22.840, the functional requirements corresponding to the rUCs in TR 38.848 were defined. These requirements cover aspects such as communication, positioning and location services, device and service management, information collection, network capability exposure, charging models, and security. Moreover, TS 22.369 also provides some general KPI definitions for some of the rUC.

In addition to the standardization efforts within 3GPP, the IEEE is also focusing on A-IoT. The IEEE 802.11bp Ambient Power (AMP) Task Group started a technical investigation to support A-IoT devices over wireless local area networks (WLANs). In March 2023, the group published a technical report titled “Support of Ambient IoT Devices in WLAN” (IEEE 802.11-23/0436r0) [47], which explores the requirements, challenges, and possible enhancements to the IEEE 802.11 standard to include A-IoT. The report identifies use cases that show how A-IoT devices can be integrated into WLAN environments. Each use case imposes different requirements in terms of energy efficiency, data collection frequency, network access procedures, and device identification mechanisms. Table 3.2 shows a summary of these use cases.

Table 3.2: Use cases defined in IEEE 802.11-23/0436r0 "Support of Ambient IoT Devices in WLAN" [47].

Use Case	Description
Smart Manufacturing	Real-time tracking of assets, workers, and products using low-cost and battery-free devices for dense deployment.
Data Center	Environmental and asset monitoring through wireless sensors. Shares similar requirements with smart manufacturing: battery-free, long-life, and low-maintenance.
Logistics/Warehouse	Accurate inventory checks and sorting using battery-free tags. Needs high identification accuracy, small size, and support for moving items.
Smart Home	Compact low-power sensors for safety, comfort, and locating personal items within home environments.
Smart Agriculture	Monitoring environmental conditions and assets in large outdoor areas. Requires wide coverage, battery-free operation, and the ability to handle thousands of devices.
Indoor Positioning	Navigation and tracking in large indoor spaces. Needs high-density, low-cost tags with 1–3 m horizontal and 1–2 m vertical accuracy.
Smart Power Grid	Monitoring equipment and environmental conditions in substations and transmission lines with battery-free, low-maintenance sensors with long-range coverage.
Fresh Food Supply Chain	Tracking of food transport conditions using ultra-low-cost, battery-free devices with long intervals between data transmissions.

3.2 European Research and Innovation Projects

Beyond standardization activities in 3GPP and IEEE, several European research and innovation projects have contributed to the definition of use cases aligned with A-IoT. Although not all of these projects explicitly use the term "Ambient IoT", many of them address its key enablers. Table 3.3 provides an overview of some of the European projects that present use cases with strong compatibility with A-IoT.

The ADROIT6G project focuses on enabling distributed intelligence for 6G AI and cloud-native networks. Some of its use cases defined in [48], [49] can also be applied to A-IoT:

- Assisting First Responders: ultra-low-power wearables can be used to transmit medical and environmental data without battery replacement,
- Rail Automation supported by Non-Terrestrial Networks: A-IoT nodes can harvest ambient energy and send reports via satellite links, minimizing maintenance costs,
- Collaborative Construction Robots: self-powered sensors can continuously report status data to nearby robots in the construction environment, giving robots the necessary context to coordinate movements, avoid obstacles, and adjust tasks as site conditions change.

The Hexa-X project, which is a flagship project for 6G vision, defines five main use case families: Sustainable Development, Immersive Telepresence for Enhanced Interactions, Local Trust Zones for Human and Machine, Massive Twinning, and Robots and Cobots [50]. A-IoT can complement four of them:

- Sustainable Development: self-powered sensors and actuators can be deployed in the 6G ecosystem, enhancing energy efficiency and reducing maintenance costs,
- Local Trust Zones for Human and Machine: ENDS can provide short-range data collection and distributed intelligence at the edge, thus enabling low-latency decision making,
- Massive Twinning: energy-harvesting sensor arrays can enable digital-twin platforms with continuous status updates on infrastructure or industrial assets, ensuring that virtual replicas remain up-to-date without power-hungry or complex logistics,
- Robots and Cobots: ENDS can be embedded in workspaces to guide and coordinate and command collaborative robots.

In the Hexa-X-II project, which continues the work performed in Hexa-X, many of the use case families mirror those of Hexa-X, and four—Collaborative Robots, Physical Awareness, Digital Twins, and Trusted Environments—remain compatible with A-IoT [51].

The IntelloT project develops integrated, distributed, human-centred and trustworthy IoT frameworks applicable to a number of scenarios [52], [53]. Three use cases in which A-IoT can be potentially applied are proposed in this project:

- Agriculture: A-IoT devices can harvest energy from sunlight, thermal gradients, or RF sources to provide environmental data, reducing maintenance costs and supporting sustainable farming,
- Healthcare: A-IoT wearables can be used to monitor medical data without frequent battery replacements, enabling long-term remote care and minimizing electronic waste.
- Manufacturing: A-IoT devices embedded on equipment can eliminate battery maintenance of sensors that monitor machine performance, enabling predictive maintenance and process optimization while integrating into existing Industrial IoT networks.

In the REINDEER project, four application scenarios are introduced: Adaptive Robotized Logistics, Human-Machine Interaction in Care Environments, Immersive Entertainment for Crowds, and Smart Homes [54]. A-IoT can be applied to three of its four use cases.

- Adaptive Robotized Logistics: END can be used in warehouse infrastructure and autonomous vehicles, enabling continuous tracking of goods and route optimization without battery replacement,
- Human-Machine Interaction in Care Environments: sensors powered by body heat or ambient light can monitor medical and environmental conditions, supporting assisted living without frequent maintenance,
- Smart Homes: A-IoT sensors can be used to monitor or modify the environmental conditions of the house, as well as to monitor its structural conditions to enable predictive maintenance.

In the SUPERIoT project, three main application scenarios are analysed: Smart Tags and Labels, Large-scale Sensing and Actuation, and Enhanced IoT Communications in Demanding Environments [55]. Each of these three application scenarios are divided into more concise use cases. A-IoT technology can be applied to the three main application scenarios of SUPERIoT as follows:

- **Smart Tags and Labels:** A-IoT tags can be attached to market products, healthcare equipment in hospitals and medical centres, industrial equipment in factories and production lines, or even pets for tracking and monitoring. This enables sustainable and low-cost tracking and location in multiple scenarios.
- **Large-scale Sensing and Actuation:** ENDS can be used to monitor and actuate over large scale like smart buildings and facilities, construction environments, smart cities and rural locations. This is possible thanks to the low maintenance requirements and long autonomy of ENDS.
- **Enhanced IoT Communications in Demanding Environments:** A-IoT is difficult to implement in this application scenario due to the particularly high level of security and privacy required. However, ENDS can be used as sensors in on-body/in-body applications or in remote zones to deploy efficient, low-maintenance and long-lasting networks.

Table 3.3: European research and innovation projects.

Project Name	Focus	Relevance to A-IoT.	Reference
ADROIT6G	AI and cloud-native design for 6G.	Involves intelligent, context-aware connectivity for massive low-cost devices.	[48], [49]
Hexa-X	Flagship for 6G vision and architecture.	Introduces concepts like ambient connectivity, massive IoT, and 6G location services.	[50]
Hexa-X-II	Continuation of Hexa-X with system-level pilots.	Considers extreme energy efficiency and ultra-dense IoT devices deployment in 6G.	[51]
IntelloT	Integrated, distributed, human-centred and trustworthy IoT framework in healthcare, farming and industry.	Energy-aware IoT network management, application function allocation, edge computing, AI/ML...	[52], [53]
REINDEER	Cell-free, distributed beamforming and distributed intelligent processing.	Enables energy-efficient, programmable wireless environments for ubiquitous sensing and tracking, as well as interaction with ENDS.	[54]
SUPERIOT	Sustainable, flexible and adaptable IoT system based on optical and radio communications.	Develops IoT nodes based on energy harvesting to enhance energy efficiency and environmental sustainability.	[55]

Chapter 4

Use Cases: AMBIENT-6G Vision

In this chapter, we present a structured analysis of use cases for A-IoT technology from the AMBIENT-6G vision, showing how ENDS can address real world challenges across multiple domains. We begin by categorizing use cases into principal families and then examine representative scenarios within each category to highlight specific requirements and considerations.

4.1 Interpretation of the Use Case Analysis

Within the AMBIENT-6G project, three use case families have been defined: (i) **hard-to-reach devices**, where devices embedded into materials or deployed in remote locations are hard and costly to access; (ii) **massive-scale sensor networks**, where although devices may be easily accessible, the scale of the deployment causes maintenance to be extremely time-consuming, costly, and environmentally unsustainable; and (iii) **extreme-lifetime applications**, where battery replacement may be feasible, but unwanted due to reasons like ease-of-use or maintenance-free time requirement.

In this chapter, eleven use cases are presented, each mapped to one or more of the three use case families defined in AMBIENT-6G. For every use case, a description and a detailed analysis of its functional requirements, KPIs and KVIs is provided. Furthermore, the END classification developed in AMBIENT-6G's deliverable **D2.1: END Architecture, Technology Trade-Off and Characterization** [1] is used to determine which types of ENDS are best suited for each use case, ensuring that device design choices align with the specific energy-harvesting, communication, and operational demands of the use case. Four different END classes were defined in deliverable D2.1:

- **Class 1 - Ultra-passive (UP) ENDS:** they have no or minimal energy storage and rely on backscattering communication;
- **Class 2 - Duty-cycled barebone (DB) ENDS:** they have energy storage through tiny supercapacitors and have intermittent communication when enough energy is available;
- **Class 3 - Duty-cycled persistent (DP) ENDS:** they have energy storage through robust supercapacitors or small batteries and have intermittent but reliable communication;
- **Class 4 - Continuous operation (CO) ENDS:** they have energy storage through batteries and support active communication.

Regarding the analysis of the functional requirements, it is organized into seven broad categories that serve to systematically describe them for each use case, ensuring alignment with ongoing standardization efforts and facilitating a clear mapping between use case demands and device/network design. The categories are as follows:

- **Communication:** specifies how **ENDs** exchange information with other nodes and the rest of the infrastructure in **A-IoT** networks. These requirements also include the selection of physical-layer methods, distinguishing between passive backscatter techniques that modulate existing **RF** signals, and active transmission modes in which devices generate their own **RF** carriers for communication. Moreover, communication requirements specify reliability methods to maintain quality of service, including error correction mechanisms and retransmission strategies.
- **Positioning/Location:** defines capabilities to determine and report position or location within an **A-IoT** network, including methods such as received signal strength (**RSS**)-based ranging, time-of-flight (**ToF**) measurements, angle-of-arrival (**AOA**) estimation, or hybrid techniques. Configurable update functions are covered, enabling position reports to be generated periodically or in response to specific events. Scenarios and spatial granularity of the position/location functions are also analysed.
- **Management:** analyses how **A-IoT** networks support device register and obtain network configuration parameters. Configuration management capabilities are covered, including the receipt and application of operational parameters or policy updates via lightweight and energy-aware protocols. Firmware and software update mechanisms and health monitoring functions are addressed, detailing how **ENDs** can perform over-the-air updates and report status, alarms, and performance metrics.
- **Collected Information and Network Exposure:** defines the data that **ENDs** must gather, and how this data should be formatted. Privacy functions like data anonymisation and user-consent management are also defined to ensure compliance with emerging **IoT** privacy regulation. Security requirements and confidentiality mechanisms for secure telemetry reporting are tackled, guaranteeing that operational and diagnostic data is transmitted without unauthorized access.
- **Energy:** defines how **ENDs** harvest, store, and manage power to sustain sensing and communication without conventional batteries. Energy sources from which **ENDs** harvest energy (e.g. photovoltaic, thermoelectric, piezoelectric, **RF** signals) are covered. Functions that manage energy allocation across sensing, processing, and communication tasks, enabling dynamic adjustment of operational modes are also addressed. Moreover, predictive energy-harvesting models are included in this analysis, which allows to anticipate energy inflows and to schedule high-consumption activities when sufficient power is available.
- **User-Safety and Robustness:** specifies the capabilities to protect users and systems under all conditions. Self-diagnostic routines that periodically check **END** health are covered, enabling shutdown in case of critical errors. Environmental protection functions to maintain operation in harsh environmental scenarios are analysed, including automatic adaptation when conditions threaten device operation. Protection measurements for users against electric shocks, burns or other hazards are also included in the analysis.

- **AI/ML:** defines the capabilities for embedding intelligent algorithms in ENDS and A-IoT networks. Model size and complexity, on-device data preprocessing, secure and efficient model update mechanisms, and standardized interfaces for integration with edge and cloud platforms are covered. Moreover, energy efficiency is considered when defining AI/ML functional requirements.

For the KPIs analysis, similarly to the procedure followed with the functional requirements, four KPI categories are defined:

- Device KPIs,
- Network KPIs,
- Application KPIs,
- AI/ML KPIs.

This ensures that networks (ranging from devices to high-layer services) can meet the requirements of A-IoT. Table 4.1 shows all the KPIs used in the analysis. It is important to note that both the specific KPIs selected and the KPI categories are highly dependent on the requirements and objectives of each individual use case. As a result, not all the KPIs apply to all the use cases.

On the other hand, KVI

s are used to evaluate how A-IoT positively contributes in each use case to sustainability goals, social well-being, economic efficiency, and technological innovation. This approach enables a standardized but flexible comparison of use cases, ensuring that selected scenarios not only meet functional and performance requirements, but also impact our lives in multiple dimensions. The impact of each A-IoT use case in four dimensions:

- **Environmental KVI**s: they consider the impact that the application of A-IoT in each use case has on the environment, including reducing pollution, using recyclable materials, or reducing e-waste.
- **Social KVI**s: they consider the impact of A-IoT on the society, including benefits to people's well-being, the integration of disadvantaged groups, or the promotion of gender equality.
- **Economic KVI**s: they consider the impact of A-IoT on the economy of both individual users and industries that may implement A-IoT in different use cases. This includes factors such as savings in maintenance, replacement or waste management.
- **Innovation KVI**s: they consider the impact of A-IoT on the development and optimization of technologies, algorithms or strategies that allow enhancing the performance and energy efficiency of communication networks.

For each dimension, an Impact Score approach is employed, assigning values from 1 (very low impact) to 5 (very high impact). Each of these values have the following meaning:

- **Impact Score 1** → **very low impact:** the use of A-IoT in the use case does not add significant value.
- **Impact Score 2** → **low impact:** the use of A-IoT in the use case provides some value, but not enough to be considered beneficial.

- **Impact Score 3** → **noticeable impact**: the use of A-IoT in the use case provides some positive value and benefits, although it also entails certain disadvantages.
- **Impact Score 4** → **high impact**: the use of A-IoT in the use case brings significant positive benefits in exchange for few or no negative effects.
- **Impact Score 5** → **very high impact**: the use of A-IoT in the use case provides differential benefits that make A-IoT stand out with respect to other implementations.

In each use case described next, the Impact Score assigned to each of the KVI dimensions is justified, covering both positive and negative impacts (including possible mitigation strategies). It is important to remark that the KVI analysis is complex, as it aims to quantify future factors that are often abstract and difficult to anticipate. For this reason, this KVI analysis, which comes from the expertise of the AMBIENT-6G partners, should be considered as preliminary. In-depth assessments (like life cycle assessment (LCA)-based analysis) and further investigation on END capabilities are needed in the future to improve it.

To facilitate reader access to all the information contained in this deliverable, Table 4.2 has been included, which presents all the Use Cases with the corresponding link to the section that describes them in depth, their Use Case Families, the compatible END Classes and the KVI Impact Scores for each of the dimensions considered.

Table 4.1: KPIs defined for the use case analysis.

KPI Category	KPI	Definition
Device	Sensing accuracy	Degree to which the value measured by an END matches the actual value of a physical quantity.
	Device autonomy	Amount of time an END can operate independently without needing to be recharged or handled for maintenance.
	Average power consumption	Mean amount of electrical power consumed by an END.
	Peak power consumption	Maximum amount of electrical power consumed by an END.
Network	End-to-end latency	Time it takes for a data packet to travel from the source to the destination across a network, including processing and transmission delays. It only accounts for successful communication events.
	Message size	Amount of data contained in a single message or transmission.
	Age of information	Time elapsed since the most recently received update was generated at the source.
	Packet loss rate	Ratio between number of packets lost and total transmission attempts.
	Communication range	Maximum distance over which an END can reliably transmit and receive data. It includes intermediate nodes in multi-hop systems.
	Service area dimension	Physical area within which a service or network can operate effectively.
	Maximum number of simultaneous devices	Highest number of devices that can be connected and operate concurrently within the system.
	Transfer interval	Time between consecutive data transmissions from an END.
	Device speed	Rate at which an END can move while maintaining reliable performance.
	User-experienced data rate	Actual data throughput perceived by the end user.
Application	Communication service availability	Percentage of time that the communication service is available.
	Positioning/location service availability	Percentage of time that the positioning or location service is available. Positioning refers to the position of a device in a coordinate system. Location refers to the relative position within a known environment.
	Positioning/location service accuracy	Closeness between the reported position and the actual physical location of a device or user.
	Command service availability	Percentage of time that the command service is available.
	AI/ML capabilities	System's ability to leverage AI and ML techniques to enhance performance or automate decisions.
AI/ML	Training complexity	The level of computational resources required to train an AI or ML model.
	Inferencing accuracy	Percentage of outputs by a trained model that match expected result.
	Inferencing latency	Time it takes or a trained model to produce an output after receiving an input.

Table 4.2: Summary of the Use Cases defined in this deliverable.

Use Case	Use Case Family			END Classes				KVI's Impact Score			
	Hard-to-reach devices	Massive-scale sensor networks	Extreme-lifetime applications	UP ENDs	DB ENDs	DP ENDs	CO ENDs	Environmental	Social	Economic	Innovation
Electronic Shelf Label								3	3	4	4
Sensors in Smart Homes								3	4	2	2
Smart Bridge Health Monitoring								3	4	5	2
Personal Belongings Finding								5	4	4	3
In-body or Wearable Medical Sensor								3	5	3	4
Smart Agriculture								5	4	4	4
Asset, Product, Tool, and Item Tracking								3	3	5	4
Museum Guide								3	3	3	4
End-to-end Logistics								3	4	4	3
Industrial Predictive Maintenance								5	3	4	4
Cooperative Mobile Robots								3	2	4	4

4.2 Electronic Shelf Label

Table 4.3: Use Case Families for Electronic Shelf Label use case.

Use Case Families		
Hard-to-reach devices	Massive-scale sensor networks	Extreme-lifetime applications

Table 4.4: END classes for Electronic Shelf Label use case.

END Classes			
UP ENDs	DB ENDs	DP ENDs	CO ENDs

4.2.1 Description

The use of electronic shelf label (ESL) tags is becoming more widespread on retail shelves that house large numbers of products. The ESL tag provides information about the price of a product, along with other potential parameters, such as the expiration date, sales offers, bar codes, quick response (QR) codes, etc. ESL tags are usually in front of a product or a group of products on the shelf, providing a convenient way to manage or update product information or set dynamic pricing over-the-air (OTA), using a mobile handheld reader (connected to a radio unit e.g., Macro basestation), or static on-site (Micro basestation), or remote reader (connected via an intermediate node) accompanied by a user-friendly application interface. This approach saves considerable time and labour costs compared to commonly used static labels (e.g., paper labels), while also enhancing the shopping experience [45].

A typical ESL tag is composed of several components that are required for communication and information display, including the RF module, MCU, battery, and display unit. To manage the information on the ESL tag, communication occurs via a wireless link between the tag and the reader connected to a server application. Some examples of wireless technologies include RF, infrared, bluetooth [56], and visible light [57], where each technology offers a different level of reliability and range.

Among the different available technologies, radio frequency identification (RFID)-based communication offers a significant advantage of low infrastructure costs. However, this comes at the expense of poorer quality-of-service (QoS) compared to other communication technologies, which have extensive protocol stacks, dedicated spectra, and centralized control to support OTA communication.

4.2.2 Functional Requirements

Communication

ESL tags must support unique identification within a local service area. The tag identifier can include third-party components in addition to the device unique identifier (UID) assigned by the core network (CN). The third party can ensure the uniqueness of tag UIDs within their

Figure 4.1: Illustration of Electronic Shelf Label use case.

local service area, such as warehouses, shopping malls, grocery stores, etc, and thus relax the constraints on ensuring uniqueness on a global scale.

The abundance of tags within a small service area mandates that communication protocols should include features for robust resource selection, such as efficient random access and effective collision resolution techniques to support bulk operations, e.g., bulk write operations. Additionally, the wireless channels experience temporary shadow fades due to obstacles, i.e., moving carts, humans, robots near shelves, aisles, etc. Therefore, it is essential to support multi-reader operation to circumvent temporary coverage holes and ensure high availability.

Positioning/Location

Given that in this use case all ESL-based ENDS have static locations, updates to their spatial positioning during runtime are not required. A third party ensures the mapping of ESL tags and their spatial context in a database, which is maintained as part of the application's functionality.

Management

Regarding management, the system must be equipped with features and mechanisms to ensure:

- permanent disabling, decommissioning, and/or off-boarding of ENDS,
- temporary enabling and disabling,
- activation-on-demand for newly deployed ENDS,
- software/firmware updates via centralized, automated provisioning and configuration,
- group operation,
- security management (at the CN and application levels, at a minimum),
- fault detection,

- multi-reader operation, and
- ENDS ownership management, particularly if the device UID includes third-party components.

Network Security

The network must be equipped with robust security protocols designed for low-power IoT systems to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of the information handled by ENDS. The system should support strong authentication procedures for ESL by network nodes, as well as additional authentication procedures for network nodes at the tag/device side, if the ENDS' capabilities allow.

Energy

The ESL-based ENDS would typically be placed in indoor environments, or at the very least, in areas where natural ambient energy sources are limited. Therefore, to operate effectively, ENDS must support energy harvesting from RF, visible light, or both. To ensure reliable operation and longer transmission duration, ENDS must incorporate a small energy storage unit (e.g., capacitor, micro-battery, or supercapacitor) to maintain functionality during temporary unavailability of ambient energy sources.

For ESL tags intended for outdoor use, the storage unit must be robust enough to withstand corrosive environmental conditions (such as moisture, unmanned vehicle (UV) radiation, dust, etc.) over extended periods. Especially in applications involving dynamic pricing, the ENDS should support features like rapid charging under low input power conditions (ranging from μW to mW) to facilitate relatively strenuous transmission operations.

User-Safety and Robustness

The use case is predominantly an indoor scenario, and therefore, variations in humidity and temperature should not be drastic. Consequently, the ENDS can be designed to operate under more relaxed conditions, with a relatively narrower range for temperature and humidity. On the other hand, the use case requires frequent handling of products by customers (e.g., picking up, touching, etc.), which may expose the ENDS to frequent shocks and vibrations. From this perspective, the ENDS should be designed with shock and vibration-absorbing materials or be robust enough to withstand such conditions. Additionally, they should be compact enough to maintain user comfort and object functionality, but not so compact that they cause difficulty for customers when reading information from the ESL-equipped liquid crystal display (LCD). The most important consideration is that END tags should be manufactured using non-toxic materials.

AI/ML

For extremely passive ENDS, employing AI/ML techniques on the devices would be challenging due to uncertainty in energy availability, limited energy storage, and low processing capabilities. However, for relatively capable ENDS, such techniques can be deployed to understand customer engagement, behavioural choices, and product demand, especially if the ESL tag is supplemented

with additional hardware, sensors and infrastructure, such as energy systems to support large processing cost, or sensor like infrared sensor to detect customer proximity or interest.

Alternatively, the AI/ML techniques can be deployed on the reader side (base station, or intermediate user equipment (UE)), or in the cloud. These techniques can enhance customer engagement analysis, helping to boost business output. Additionally, they can assist with channel and radio conditions estimation and error corrections, thus improving the communication link.

4.2.3 Key Performance Indicators

Table 4.5: KPIs for Electronic Shelf Label use case.

Device KPIs		Network KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Sensing accuracy	N.A.	End-to-end latency	< 1 s
Device autonomy	> 20 years	Age of information	N.A.
Avg. power consumption	< 10 μ W	Packet loss rate	< 1 %
Peak power consumption	< 100 μ W	Message size	< 100 Bytes
		Communication range	< 50 m
		Service area dimension	< 20000 m ²
		Max simultaneous devices	< 30000 devices
		Transfer interval	0.3 - 2 hours
		Device speed	Static
		User-experienced data rate	0.8 kbps
Application KPIs		AI/ML KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Communication service availability	> 99.9 %	Training complexity	N.A.
Positioning/Location service availability	Not required	Inferencing accuracy	N.A.
Positioning/Location service accuracy	N.A.	Inferencing latency	N.A.
Command service availability	Not required		
AI/ML capabilities	Not required		

4.2.4 Key Value Indicators

Environmental KVIs

Impact Score: 3 Traditional labelling methods typically rely on RFID-based technology or manual labelling, both of which have environmental impacts. RFID integration requires precise implementation, and often includes batteries which need to be replaced periodically. This increases costs and requires additional human effort. Moreover, the communication links are not always optimal, leading to higher energy consumption (due to increased collisions or retransmissions), as well as the need for denser deployment of readers, which increases infrastructure costs, material costs, and puts additional strain on the resources.

At the same time, ESLs contribute to sustainability by reducing paper waste (typically used in paper tags), as well as minimizing food and product waste through better management, tracking, and updates.

On the other hand, manual labelling requires a significant human presence, leading to delays and being highly prone to errors. This results in waste of human effort, which could be minimized through automation with better-equipped technology, such as ESL.

Social KVs

Impact Score: 3 ESLs have a modest social impact by enhancing both the customer and shopping experience and store efficiency. Their use in businesses increases transparency by providing regular, fast, and accurate pricing updates. They also save time by reducing human errors and infrequent customer queries associated with paper tags and can ensure faster checkouts if ESLs integrated with the point-of-sale (POS) system. Furthermore, with dynamic pricing strategies, ESLs can help accelerate the sale of products with near-expiry dates through targeted discounts and sales, thus reducing wastage.

Economic KVs

Impact Score: 4 ESLs provides a significant economic impact for retailers, store owners, or warehouse managers by reducing costs and improving revenue. Although there may be substantial initial costs for infrastructure deployment, these can be outweighed by the gains, especially with large-scale utilization in supermarkets or hypermarkets, mega marts, malls, and similar venues. ESLs offer a highly automated solution that reduces pricing errors and incorrect pricing, significantly minimizing financial losses. They also lower costs associated with labour for manual label changes or order fulfilment when integrated with the POS system, as well as material costs for paper, ink, and printing used in traditional paper tags. Furthermore, ESLs ensures efficient inventory management by enabling real-time tracking and reducing waste. Additionally, they facilitate dynamic pricing, which can potentially increase revenue through targeted promotions and price optimization.

Innovation KVs

Impact Score: 4 ESL tags powered by ambient sources running on cellular technologies can offer a wide range of diverse and rich features. Some of these features can be remotely managed if not directly incorporated into the ESL tags due to their small form factor. This allows businesses to optimize operations, reduce costs, and minimize waste. The data collected from tags can be combined with other sensors, such as temperature or infrared sensors, depending on the use case, to enable improved data analysis and prediction. For example, a temperature sensor could allow ESL tags to dynamically adjust expiration times/dates or modify the prices of temperature-sensitive food items.

In summary, the innovation will be driven by the following indicators, which will propel the adoption of ambient-powered ESL tags in the retail world:

- battery-less (reduces cost, easy adoption and offers more flexibility),
- utilization cellular technologies' features, centralized control, reliable communication link, rich data collection, analysis, and prediction features.

Figure 4.2: Impact Scores for Electronic Shelf Label.

4.3 Sensors in Smart Homes

Table 4.6: Use Case Families for Sensors in Smart Homes use case.

Use Case Families		
Hard-to-reach devices	Massive-scale sensor networks	Extreme-lifetime applications

Table 4.7: END classes for Sensors in Smart Homes use case.

END Classes			
UP ENDs	DB ENDs	DP ENDs	CO ENDs

4.3.1 Description

In the last decade, smart homes have seen an increase in popularity due to their improved comfort and quality of life, and the way they can transform our daily lives. In such smart homes, everyday devices and appliances (such as thermostats, lights, refrigerators, ovens, etc.) get connected to a central monitoring and control unit, often connected to the Internet for remote access. This reshapes the way we engage with our home environment, potentially enhancing energy efficiency, sustainability, home security and health outcomes. However, getting everyday objects smart by connecting them to the internet makes them vulnerable to hacking (security and privacy), has a certain level of complexity, and costs money. This use case addresses another hidden challenge inside smart homes. Smart objects require extra hardware for (i) communicating with the central controller in case of wireless connection, and for (ii) processing the incoming or outgoing information to or from the device, increasing the power consumption at each unit. Research shows that in smart lighting [58], [59] the standby power consumption of the electronics for smart Light Emitting Diode (LED) bulbs' control and radio communication lies around 0.4 W, resulting in an additional 3.5 kWh per year. The active power of a LED bulb lies around 10 W for a 800 Lm lamp. This means that every 20 hours, a smart lamp uses as much as a generic LED lamp in active mode during 1 hour. RF backscatter communication in indoor environments in combination with ultra-low power designs can counteract this unseen energy consumption. In this use case, we explore how we can set up an indoor backscattering network for monitoring of ambient parameters (light, temperature, air quality). These devices operate without an integrated power supply by leveraging backscatter communication, wherein they modulate and reflect incident RF signals emitted by an external RF source to transmit data. The information that will be added to the channel consists of small data packets with a low update rate. An example of the smart home with backscattering integration is depicted in Figure 4.3. It consists of several ENDs, capturing, processing and transmitting the received sensor data and a central controller that receives, demodulates and processes the backscattered sensor data.

Figure 4.3: Illustration of Sensors in Smart Homes use case. Typical examples are temperature, humidity, air quality, water and power consumption and presence detection sensors.

4.3.2 Functional Requirements

Communication

The system shall enable ultra-low-power, low-throughput communication between semi-passive backscatter ENDS and UEs by leveraging a custom backscatter modulation scheme. The protocol must support sufficient data rates to facilitate the periodic transmission of sensor readings to a central controller, while maintaining minimal active power draw on the tag side. Communication should be optimized for short-range, asymmetric links, with emphasis on tag simplicity and reader-side processing complexity.

The custom backscatter communication protocol shall incorporate lightweight but effective synchronization primitives and error detection mechanisms, such as preamble-based timing alignment and cyclic redundancy check (CRC), to ensure data integrity. To account for the challenges inherent to reflective and interference-prone RF environments, the protocol should support adaptive symbol timing, collision avoidance through time or frequency domain separation, frequency hopping, code division-multiple access (CDMA), to enable scalable, collision-resistant operation and robust envelope detection strategies. Additional redundancy or forward error correction (FEC) may be integrated as needed based on the application's reliability requirements.

The communication stack should be designed for seamless integration with commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) mobile and IoT devices by employing standard-compliant physical and MAC layer abstractions where applicable. While leveraging custom backscatter modulation techniques, the protocol should maintain compatibility with widely adopted wireless frameworks (e.g., BLE, Wi-Fi, or sub-GHz industrial, scientific and medical (ISM) bands) through proxy gateways or protocol translation layers. This ensures scalable deployment and interoperability within heterogeneous IoT ecosystems, while facilitating straightforward user access via smartphones or other existing infrastructure.

The system must support concurrent interactions from multiple backscatter tags or user devices within a shared RF domain without incurring packet collisions or identity ambiguities. Tag identification must be robust against signal interference and closely spaced transmissions, ensuring

accurate differentiation and tracking of multiple active entities in dynamic environments.

Positioning/Location

The system architecture shall not actively determine or update the spatial positioning of energy-neutral devices during runtime. Instead, device commissioning, including the assignment of spatial context, shall be conducted manually during initial system setup. To minimize complexity and conserve energy, spatial granularity should be limited to the room or zone level rather than requiring precise localization. This approach aligns with the constraints of energy-harvesting devices and supports scalable deployment in infrastructure-limited environments.

Management

Energy neutral devices shall embed a UID within their transmitted payloads, ensuring traceable association between sensor data or device state and the originating hardware instance. This UID is critical for the aforementioned system commissioning, enabling deterministic mapping of data streams to specific devices during deployment and operation. While spatial metadata, such as room-level location, should be defined during initial setup, the system shall support controlled updates to this metadata to accommodate reconfiguration or relocation.

The system should support configurable mechanisms to temporarily or permanently disable non-critical ambient IoT sensors, thereby optimizing energy usage and minimizing unnecessary RF activity. This functionality should be controllable via centralized policies or local triggers, allowing for dynamic adaptation to environmental conditions, user preferences, or operational priorities.

To ensure operational integrity, devices must undergo periodic health checks to verify active status, functional correctness, and communication reliability. Fault conditions (e.g., transmission failures, sensor anomalies, or energy depletion) shall be logged and flagged for maintenance. Furthermore, performance metrics, including signal strength, data latency, and activity frequency, should be continuously monitored and analysed to inform diagnostics, support predictive maintenance, and ensure long-term system robustness.

Collected Information and Network Exposure

Devices shall transmit user-associated telemetry, such as environmental readings (e.g., temperature) or device state information, to the central controller for purposes including system analytics, behavioural inference, or personalization. While the transmitted data may appear non-sensitive in isolation, appropriate safeguards must be implemented to preserve user privacy. All data must be anonymized or pseudonymized in accordance with established privacy standards, ensuring that individuals cannot be directly identified through the dataset without authorized correlation.

Back-end systems must provide mechanisms for secure data access, with full support for user-initiated data erasure and auditing of stored records. Furthermore, the system architecture shall incorporate robust cybersecurity measures, including authentication, encryption, access control, and intrusion detection, to safeguard against unauthorized access, data breaches, and malicious tampering.

Energy

This use case depends on device classes requiring limited data buffering or short-duration computational tasks (e.g., Class 3 devices). The integration of small-scale energy storage elements, such as supercapacitors or high-efficiency capacitors may be employed. These storage components enable transient high-power operations, such as time-critical response coordination or data framing, while preserving the system's overall ultra-low power footprint. In short-term deployments, small battery-assisted tags may be provisionally utilized. However, this strategy is generally discouraged due to environmental concerns associated with battery disposal and the regulatory implications of hazardous material classification. In some scenarios, ambient light harvesting can enable long-term, batteryless operation.

User-Safety and Robustness

RF emissions from the system must adhere to all applicable regional regulatory standards (e.g., Federal Communications Commission (FCC), European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)), ensuring compliance with spectral power density limits and interference thresholds. Devices shall be designed to operate in a non-intrusive manner, exhibiting minimal electromagnetic or physical impact on their immediate environment. In the event of system failure, communication loss, or degraded performance, critical fallback functionalities, such as manual control interfaces (e.g., light switch activation), must remain accessible to the user. Furthermore, the system shall support autonomous fault recovery mechanisms, enabling self-reconfiguration or re-synchronisation without user intervention to restore nominal operation. This is possible with low-power watchdog timers, monitoring firmware execution and trigger system resets or safe state fallback if abnormal behaviour is detected. Periodic diagnostics or health beacons (where energy budget permits) can provide minimal status updates to indicate connectivity, sensor state, or charge status of local energy storage.

AI/ML

Advanced signal processing at the central processing unit (access point (AP)) side, such as adaptive filtering and interference suppression, can enhance tag detection in challenging RF backscatter environments, particularly in multipath-rich or spectrally congested conditions. While such techniques are valuable, many smart home applications currently rely on simpler processing approaches, which will be benchmarked against AI/ML-based methods.

A-IoT models can be leveraged at the system level to analyse user interaction patterns, environmental sensor data, and actuation behaviour. These models enable energy optimization, climate control adaptation, and support automated device commissioning, reducing manual setup efforts.

Additionally, ML models play a key role in predictive maintenance by detecting anomalies such as irregular RSS or delayed responses. A notable application is the early detection of faults in household battery systems or power electronics, helping prevent hazards such as overheating or fire, while maintaining a lightweight footprint on individual devices.

However, in many practical smart home use cases, such complexity may not be necessary, basic signal processing techniques are often sufficient to achieve reliable performance, particularly in static, low-interference environments. As part of the system evaluation, AI/ML models should

be benchmarked against both basic and advanced signal processing approaches to assess the trade-offs in detection accuracy, computational overhead, and energy consumption.

To preserve the ultra-low-power profile of near-passive backscatter devices, AI/ML processing should not be deployed on the device side, but rather centralized at the receiver or system backend, where energy and computational resources are less constrained.

4.3.3 Key Performance Indicators

Table 4.8: KPIs for Smart Homes use case.

Device KPIs		Network KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Sensing accuracy	> 95 %	End-to-end latency	< 10 min
Device autonomy	> 20 years	Age of information	N.A.
Avg. power consumption	< 50 μ W	Packet loss rate	< 5 %
Peak power consumption	< 1 mW	Message size	< 100 Bytes
		Communication range	< 50 m
		Service area dimension	Room size
		Max simultaneous devices	< 20 devices
		Transfer interval	60 s
		Device speed	Static
		User-experienced data rate	1 kbps
Application KPIs		AI/ML KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Communication service availability	> 99.9 %	Training complexity	N.A.
Positioning/Location service availability	Not required	Inferencing accuracy	N.A.
Positioning/Location service accuracy	N.A.	Inferencing latency	N.A.
Command service availability	Not required		
AI/ML capabilities	Not required		

4.3.4 Key Value Indicators

Environmental KVs

Impact Score: 3 A-IoT technology in smart home sensor systems offers environmental benefits primarily through the reduction of electronic waste. These devices often operate without batteries and require minimal hardware, reducing both material usage and disposal needs. The simplified infrastructure on the receiver side further reduces the environmental footprint, while the long operational lifespan and reusability of backscatter devices support sustainable deployment.

However, there are potential drawbacks. The need for continuous or periodic RF illumination from centralized transmitters can increase overall power consumption, potentially offsetting the energy savings at the device level. Additionally, the environmental impact must be evaluated at the system level; poor scaling or excessive infrastructure could reduce or negate the sustainability

advantages. Its environmental value depends on careful system design and energy-efficient deployment.

Social KVs

Impact Score: 4 Independent living, particularly for elderly or vulnerable individuals, through applications such as passive fall detection and unobtrusive health monitoring can be supported. Enabling non-intrusive sensing without requiring user intervention or frequent maintenance also enhances comfort and overall well-being. These benefits are especially relevant in health-conscious environments where long-term autonomy and quality of life are key priorities.

However, there are social risks to consider. The deployment of such technology may exacerbate the digital divide, particularly for populations with limited access to digital infrastructure or low technological literacy. If not carefully designed for inclusivity, these systems could deepen existing inequalities in access to healthcare, safety, and comfort-enhancing technologies.

Economic KVs

Impact Score: 2 By eliminating batteries and reducing the complexity of hardware, these systems lower both production and maintenance costs over time. Their low-power, long-lifetime design also reduces operational expenses for users. In sectors like assisted living or energy management at home, the automation enabled by backscatter-based sensors can improve efficiency and reduce costs (e.g., by energy savings), offering long-term return on investment.

However, there are economic threats as well. Initial development and integration costs may be higher due to the need for specialized receiver infrastructure and system calibration. Market adoption could also be slowed by compatibility issues with existing commercial devices and standards. Additionally, the cost-effectiveness may diminish in small-scale deployments where the infrastructure overhead is not offset by volume or long-term gains.

Innovation KVs

Impact Score: 2 Ambient backscattering has a niche contribution to the innovative aspects within smart homes. It does not significantly advance energy efficiency beyond the device level, nor does it drive major improvements in scalability or adaptability compared to conventional IoT architectures, as it primarily enables passive data collection rather than dynamic, autonomous decision-making. As this is in an indoor environment, development efforts should focus on alternatives for the well-researched solar based energy harvesting, potentially leading to more efficient (ambient) harvesting techniques.

Figure 4.4: Impact Scores for Sensors in Smart Home.

4.4 Smart Bridge Health Monitoring

Table 4.9: Use Case Families for Smart Bridge Health Monitoring use case.

Use Case Families		
Hard-to-reach devices	Massive-scale sensor networks	Extreme-lifetime applications

Table 4.10: END classes for Smart Bridge Health Monitoring use case.

END Classes			
UP ENDs	DB ENDs	DP ENDs	CO ENDs

4.4.1 Description

Despite significant advances in structural engineering and material science, ensuring the safety and durability of bridges still requires continuous monitoring. This is largely due to the cumulative effects of natural disasters, heavy and continuous traffic loads, and gradual wear from environmental exposure. Along with variations in usage, material properties and inherent design/construction defects introduce uncertainties in a bridge’s operational behaviour that engineers must account for. On-site visual inspections may not be sufficient, as early signs of damage such as local yielding, microcracking, and changes in the constituent materials, are often undetectable to the human eye.

Up-to-date knowledge of a bridge’s structural condition is essential for damage detection and characterization, forecasting future degradation, and comprehensive risk assessment. In fact, by detecting early signs of damage, bridges’ owners can save millions in maintenance, extend the service life, and reduce the risk of casualties. More importantly, a quantifiable measure of the bridge’s reliability can guide maintenance operations to efficiently address population growth, evolving transportation methods, and changing mobility patterns.

Changes in temperature and humidity induce stress and strain in the bridge, leading to the gradual creep and shrinkage of concrete structures over time. Additionally, any initial fatigue cracks may propagate due to increased traffic load, harsh environmental conditions, design flaws, and ageing. Prolonged exposure to high humidity also corrodes metallic components, such as cables, reinforcements, and girders, potentially degrading bridge performance. Excessive erosion of stream bed or bank material around foundations can cause the bridge to become unstable and, therefore, unsafe for traffic. Vibration from external impacts, like collisions with vehicles, ships, or barges, can cause significant damage, particularly in bridges over heavy fluvial traffic. In conclusion, a variety of factors must be monitored to ensure the continued health and safety of bridges, thereby causing heterogeneous service demands from the ENDs.

Given the heterogeneous and demanding monitoring conditions outlined above, employing A-IoT systems becomes a compelling choice over traditional wired or battery-powered devices. Unlike wired solutions, A-IoT systems significantly reduce installation complexity and costs, particularly advantageous for extensive bridge structures or those located in remote locations. Furthermore,

A-IoT systems require less maintenance in the long-term compared to battery-powered sensors, which often require frequent battery replacements, increasing operational overhead and costs. Since energy harvesting and energy efficient communication and processing techniques are distinctive features of A-IoT systems, ENDS can operate continuously and autonomously, thereby providing an ecologically responsible solution.

A generalization of the smart bridge health monitoring use case is depicted in Figure 4.5 comprising multiple ENDS monitoring different physical quantities.

Figure 4.5: Illustration of Smart Bridge Health Monitoring use case.

4.4.2 Functional Requirements

Communication

When measurements are completed, they are notified upon variations beyond predefined critical thresholds to reduce communication/computation overhead. For that, the system can enable ultra-low-power and low-throughput asynchronous communication protocols to gather the data on a local gateway—installed on the bridge—and then forward pre-processed measurements for diagnostics and visualization. As monitoring demands increase and the number of active ENDS may grow, the medium can be shared using non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) architectures, while sparsity-aware signal processing can enable grant-free detection and decoding of those sparse transmissions. Ultimately, error detection and correction mechanisms are indispensable to ensure reliable diagnostics of the smart bridge health monitoring application considering the heterogeneous requirements, hardware features, and installation conditions of the ENDS.

To ensure seamless integration across different deployment scenarios, the gateways and ENDS may be equipped with a modular radio front-end that lets the system switch dynamically between short-range communications (e.g., BLE) for diagnostics, long-range low-power communications (e.g., long range (LoRa)) for sporadic measurements report, and/or high-throughput updates via Wi-Fi. A policy manager evaluates communication range, data volume, and power budget to select the optimal link, while adhering to open communication standards for interoperability. In cases where a multi-radio stack is too power-hungry, ultra-low-power ENDS can instead use

backscatter links to the nearby gateway, which can simultaneously act as ET to recharge selected ENDS.

Positioning/Location

The placement of the ENDS on the bridge will depend on the specific physical quantities to be measured, such as humidity, temperature, acceleration, and so on. Additionally, the spatial granularity of the ENDS deployment for monitoring vibration will be determined by the number and spatial characteristics of the bridge's vibration modes. The network will update the position/orientation of critical devices only when the changes in the structure of the bridge result in significant displacements of the ENDS positions; updates are applied manually whenever new devices are installed or large-scale maintenance occurs, while any minor drift will be compensated in the measured data.

Management

ENDS must be assigned UIDs to specify their relative position on the bridge and the physical quantities they monitor. To minimize maintenance and restrict it to essential interventions, the system should include protocols for periodically assessing the operational status of ENDS, such as evaluating measurement accuracy, response time, and other performance indicators derived from the collected data. These diagnostics will support early fault detection, reduce downtime, and ensure reliable long-term monitoring. Moreover, efficient over-the-air firmware updates are required to cope with the heterogeneous deployment of ENDS.

Collected Information and Network Exposure

ENDS transmit raw measurements which are directly related to the structural health of the bridge. Each measurement is implicitly associated with its geographic origin through the UID assigned to the corresponding END. Although the transmitted data does not contain any user-specific information that could compromise individual privacy, unauthorized access to the raw measurements could reveal vulnerabilities in the infrastructure, potentially exposing the bridge to targeted acts of sabotage. This is why strong authentication, access control, and encryption mechanisms are required to access the information mapping the UID with the specific location of the END and its measurements.

Energy

Managing a large number of devices with heterogeneous energy demands and installation conditions requires a combination of energy saving and energy harvesting techniques to ensure long-term and maintenance-free operation. In this context, adaptive duty-cycling strategies can be employed to optimize the finite energy stored in batteries and/or supercapacitors based on ENDS-specific communication, processing, and sensing requirements. Notably, for certain physical variables—such as vibrations or temperature—low-cost energy harvesters can be used to awaken END when the changes in the physical variables enter a region of interest, thereby reducing the active periods of the ENDS.

ENDS can incorporate energy harvesting circuits to harness energy from sunlight, wind, vibrations, and temperature changes. However, depending on how the ENDS is installed, e.g., under

the bridge or embedded into the structure, energy harvesting from ambient sources might not be viable as a stand-alone solution. This is why, the gateways can act the times of energy transmitters charging the ENDS using RF waves. Notably, the ENDS deployment and their energy requirements will affect the optimal deployment of such gateways.

User-Safety and Robustness

ENDs must operate under harsh conditions, including large temperature variations, high humidity, corrosion, and mechanical vibrations. Water/dust-proof enclosures, e.g., IP-graded, will be required to maintain the ENDS operational. In addition, physical-security measures including tamper-resistant housings, lockable mounts, and low-complexity intrusion detection mechanisms must be in place to prevent unauthorized access or vandalisms in ENDS within the reach of citizens. Finally, to ensure rapid recovery from malfunctions, ENDS should support manual or autonomous recovery mechanisms depending on the installation conditions. Manual options include hot-swappable modules for field technicians, while autonomous recovery can encompass built-in watchdogs, self-rebooting firmware, and self-healing software routines.

AI/ML

The amount of measurement data generated by the ENDS on the bridge can grow significantly over time. Notably, AI/ML-aided techniques can help reduce the volume of generated data by dynamically adjusting the thresholds that trigger sensing operations. Additionally, AI/ML methods can assist engineers responsible for bridge maintenance by detecting anomalies in the collected data, thereby helping to predict potential risks, schedule timely maintenance operations, and implement traffic restrictions or load management measures when necessary.

AI/ML techniques can also be used for communication tasks such as filtering, interference suppression, joint channel estimation and signal detection, and well as for boosting energy efficiency, e.g., via AI/ML-based duty-cycling. Notably, the application of AI/ML in this context must be optimized to operate within the limited processing power, memory, and energy constraints of ENDS, with computationally intensive workloads delegated to the gateways.

4.4.3 Key Performance Indicators

Table 4.11: KPIs for Bridge Health Monitoring use case.

Device KPIs		Network KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Sensing accuracy	Depends on magnitude	End-to-end latency	< 1 s
Device autonomy	> 20 years	Age of information	< 10 s
Avg. power consumption	< 1 mW	Packet loss rate	< 1 %
Peak power consumption	< 10 mW	Message size	< 1 kbit
		Communication range	< 100 m
		Service area dimension	Bridge size
		Max simultaneous devices	< 60 devices
		Transfer interval	< 10 s
		Device speed	Static
		User-experienced data rate	100 kbps
Application KPIs		AI/ML KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Communication service availability	> 99.9 %	Training complexity	200 MFLOPS
Positioning/Location service availability	Not required	Inferencing accuracy	> 95 %
Positioning/Location service accuracy	N.A.	Inferencing latency	< 0.1 s
Command service availability	Not required		
AI/ML capabilities	Yes		

4.4.4 Key Value Indicators

Environmental KVs

Impact Score: 3 While indirect, the environmental benefits of smart bridge health monitoring are still notable. By reducing the number and frequency of inspection trips and heavy equipment use, the system contributes to lower emissions from logistics operations. It also supports resource efficiency, as fewer reactive maintenance activities mean reduced consumption of materials and energy. Importantly, the system promotes long-term sustainability by preserving the structural integrity of the bridge, reducing the need for major renovations or replacements and thus lowering the environmental footprint over the bridge's life cycle.

Energy-saving and energy-harvesting technologies minimize (and even eliminate) the dependence on batteries. This not only prolongs the lifespan of the monitoring system but also reduces the environmental pollution associated with improper waste handling.

Social KVs

Impact Score: 4 A smart bridge health monitoring system has a high social impact, primarily by enhancing public safety. Real-time monitoring enables early detection of structural issues, significantly reducing the risk of catastrophic failure and protecting human lives. Additionally, the presence of such a system fosters community trust in infrastructure, as users will feel safer using

bridges that are continuously monitored. The system also contributes to greater accessibility and reduced disruption by minimizing the frequency and duration of closures needed for manual inspections, thus ensuring smoother traffic flow and access to essential services.

Economic KVs

Impact Score: 5 Economically, while upfront costs are higher than for unmonitored bridges due to the ENDS, gateways, and the infrastructure to support the A-IoTs network in general, the application offers substantial value by minimizing the bridge's operational costs. Through predictive maintenance, it enables timely repairs that are less costly than emergency interventions, while also extending the lifespan of the structure. The system enhances operational efficiency by reducing the need for labour-intensive inspections and allowing maintenance crews to focus on targeted areas. Furthermore, by detecting and addressing vulnerabilities early, the system helps mitigate financial risk related to liability from potential structural failures or service disruptions.

Minimizing maintenance operations on the ENDS has a significant economic impact in smart bridge health monitoring system. Considering the a large number of ENDS might be deployed on the bridge, frequent maintenance becomes costly, time-consuming, or may require traffic disruptions. Beyond direct maintenance savings, the value of smart bridge health monitoring lies in ensuring continuous service, public safety, and logistical reliability, all critical to regional economic productivity.

Innovation KVs

Impact Score: 2 Incorporating context-awareness to energy harvesting and wake-up technologies brings significant benefits to scale bridge health monitoring operations. Notably, the innovative use of A-IoT systems enables the implementation of low-complexity sensors by exploiting ambient energy sources not only to charge the ENDS, but also to infer physical magnitudes directly from the characteristics of the harvested energy. Similarly, energy harvesting circuits can serve as event-driven wake-up triggers, allowing the ENDS to remain inactive until the physical magnitude to be measured changes beyond predefined thresholds.

Figure 4.6: Impact Scores for Smart Bridge Health Monitoring.

4.5 Personal Belongings Finding

Table 4.12: Use Case Families for Personal Belongings Finding use case.

Use Case Families		
Hard-to-reach devices	Massive-scale sensor networks	Extreme-lifetime applications

Table 4.13: END classes for Personal Belongings Finding use case.

END Classes			
UP ENDs	DB ENDs	DP ENDs	CO ENDs

4.5.1 Description

In present days, people have with them and use all kinds of personal belongings in their daily lives. These personal items range from electronic devices like headphones or smartwatches, to less sophisticated items like keys, ID cards or wallets. In most cases, these personal items have a high economical or personal value, which means that losing them could represent a problem. However, the loss of personal belongings in the domestic environment affects people of all ages in all contexts on a regular basis.

Searching for these lost items can result in time loss, interruptions in daily activities, and high levels of stress and anxiety. This affects productivity and emotional well-being, and can also impact social and professional life. The A-IoT technology can provide a sustainable solution to this problem.

This use case uses A-IoT technology to enhance the everyday experience of locating misplaced personal items within a domestic environment. The system integrates END tags, which are small, low-cost, and energy-efficient devices that can be designed to be attached to personal items. These END tags enable interaction with the surrounding infrastructure without requiring constant user intervention.

When needed, the END tag gets energy from a RF signal provided by the UE of the personal item's owner (e.g. a smartphone). Additionally, other ambient energy sources can be used in order to ensure robust operation in multiple scenarios. When a personal item is lost, the owner initiates the finding procedure with their UE. The UE sends a RF signal to energize the END tag attached to the lost item and starts the positioning procedure. When energized, the END tag modulates the received RF signal relying on backscattering modulation, thus being able to respond to the UE's positioning request. Though END tags do not have active localization capabilities like Global Positioning System (GPS) due to their simplicity and power constraints, their location can be inferred through passive techniques such as signal triangulation, proximity estimation, or RF fingerprinting. By reflecting RF signals to multiple receivers like smartphones

Figure 4.7: Illustration of Personal Belongings Finding use case.

or other IoT nodes, the system can estimate the END tag's position based on signal strength, ToF or AOA data. This enables users to detect the presence of a lost item and to receive approximate location guidance, enhancing the effectiveness of the search process. With respect to other low power technologies (Ultra-Wideband (UWB), BLE, RFID...), A-IoT uses simpler and less expensive devices. Furthermore, the fact that A-IoT does not require batteries to work also represents an advantage in terms of both complexity and environmental concerns. Figure 4.7 depicts a possible scenario of the Personal Belongings Finding use case.

4.5.2 Functional Requirements

Communication

The system must support ultra-low power communications while ensuring sufficient data rates and packet sizes to enable the transmission of identifiers from END tags to UEs and IoT nodes. To guarantee reliable operation even in challenging environments, END tags located in hard-to-reach areas or regions with limited coverage must be capable of establishing communication with both UEs and IoT nodes. Robustness must be achieved with simple and efficient error detection and synchronization mechanisms, avoiding any increase in the complexity or power consumption of the END tags. END tags must rely on backscattering modulation to encode information onto external RF carriers, enabling the transmission of data to UEs and IoT nodes. Furthermore, communication should be initiated by UEs, thereby minimizing unnecessary data exchanges and enabling efficient and low-power operation.

Positioning/Location

The system must operate in all domestic environments, including bedrooms, living rooms, garages, and gardens, where signal conditions and physical layouts may vary significantly. Moreover, it should also extend its functionality outside the home, enabling users to locate items in semi-public or external places if the user has access to nearby network nodes. To ensure usability in diverse contexts, the system must offer sufficient positioning granularity to determine the location of objects in small rooms, where spatial resolution is essential for item finding.

Management

Each END tag must have a UID that allows it to be distinguished from others. The system must support the registration and association of each END tag with a specific physical object. To maintain flexibility, the system must also allow for dynamic metadata updates, enabling users to modify the object associated with a given END tag. Additionally, the system must incorporate mechanisms to periodically monitor the operational status of the tags by evaluating health indicators like backscatter signal quality and response time. Any detected faults should be logged, and users must have access to the fault history to facilitate intervention or replacement of malfunctioning ENDs tags.

Collected Information and Network Exposure

Since END tags in this use case typically remain unpowered, the amount of information they can collect is limited. Nevertheless, certain data—such as the number of activations or the most recent locations where a tag was detected—can be recorded and transmitted on demand when required by the user. To ensure the integrity and confidentiality of this information as well as privacy of user's data and location, the system must implement low-power yet robust security protocols, including data access control and encryption mechanisms, to protect communications against potential interceptions or data leaks.

Energy

The primary powering method for END tags in this use case must be WPT, as lost items may end up in locations where no ambient energy sources are available. Nonetheless, complementary energy harvesting techniques like vibration, thermal gradients, photovoltaic cells, or RF energy harvesting can be considered to support END tags operation. In scenarios where the physical size of the END tag is not a limiting factor and does not interfere with the normal use of the object to which it is attached, the use of supercapacitors or other low-energy storage elements can be considered to enhance END tag functionality. However, due to environmental considerations, such storage components should only be employed when necessary.

User-Safety and Robustness

END tags must be designed to work under different conditions, including shocks, humidity, vibrations, and wide temperature ranges. This ensures robust operation in different scenarios. At the same time, they must be compact enough not to interfere with the normal use of the personal objects to which they are attached, preserving user comfort and object functionality. Additionally, user safety must be a priority; END tags should be manufactured using non-toxic materials and must incorporate both hardware and software-level safety mechanisms to prevent malfunctions that could potentially lead to user harm.

AI/ML

Due to their low complexity and limited capabilities, it is difficult to use AI/ML techniques (including those aimed at low-power applications) in END tags. However, AI/ML can be deployed in the UE or in the cloud. These AI/ML functionalities can be used to track typical user trajectories or frequently visited locations, which can help in searching for lost objects. AI/ML

models can also be deployed in the UE to implement advanced signal processing techniques. AI/ML can help in processes like channel estimation, equalization, decoding or demodulation to reduce error rate and improve communication from END tags to UEs.

4.5.3 Key Performance Indicators

Table 4.14: KPIs for Personal Belongings Finding use case.

Device KPIs		Network KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Sensing accuracy	N.A.	End-to-end latency	< 1 s
Device autonomy	> 20 years	Age of information	< 10 s
Avg. power consumption	< 1 μ W	Packet loss rate	< 1 %
Peak power consumption	< 100 μ W	Message size	< 1 kbit
		Communication range	< 10 m
		Service area dimension	< 200 m ²
		Max simultaneous devices	< 10 devices
		Transfer interval	On user request
		Device speed	Static
		User-experienced data rate	1 kbps
Application KPIs		AI/ML KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Communication service availability	> 99.9 %	Training complexity	N.A.
Positioning/Location service availability	> 99.9 %	Inferencing accuracy	N.A.
Positioning/Location service accuracy	< 1 m	Inferencing latency	N.A.
Command service availability	Not required		
AI/ML capabilities	Not required		

4.5.4 Key Value Indicators

Environmental KVs

Impact Score: 4 The "Personal Belongings Finding" use case has a high environmental impact. Having a method of locating lost objects reduces the need to manufacture replacement units. This reduction in the replacements means less extraction of raw materials and a consequent reduction in energy consumption associated with the design, manufacturing and transportation stages.

Recovering lost items also prevents premature disposal, prolonging the life of the goods and reducing the amount of waste and e-waste. This effect translates into a reduction in the materials destined for landfills, reducing the release of harmful substances that result from the degradation of plastic and electronic components.

Moreover, the use of A-IoT for this use case compared to other technologies has advantages from an environmental point of view. END tags have reduced electronic complexity and use low-environmental-impact materials. Their manufacturing phase consumes fewer resources and

produces lower CO₂ equivalent emissions, especially in the absence of batteries [60]. During use, A-IoT generates no operational emissions from recharging and maintenance, as no batteries are used in END tags. Finally, at the end of life, the absence of batteries and heavy components in A-IoT facilitates waste management and reduces e-waste generation.

Social KVIs

Impact Score: 4 Recovering lost objects through remote location reduces the anxiety and frustration associated with lost belongings. By reducing the time spent searching for lost items, the stress caused is mitigated. Moreover, the certainty of being able to locate personal items in case of loss increases the sense of control and reduces perceived vulnerability. This effect contributes to a better social environment in which individuals feel protected against accidental losses.

Usage of END tags also contributes to the autonomy of users with limited mobility or cognitive impairment by facilitating access to their belongings without requiring assistance. This increased self-sufficiency improves self-esteem and reduces their dependence.

Economic KVIs

Impact Score: 4 From the owner's point of view, recovering lost items directly reduces the impact associated with purchasing replacement units. For example, this savings is particularly significant for high-value items, where avoiding a single replacement can offset the investment in remote location tools. For objects susceptible to duplication (keys, access cards, credit cards...), locating the original eliminates the need to pay for copying services.

From the manufacturer's point of view, by eliminating expensive and power-hungry active components, A-IoT enables volume production of END tags, so the economic cost of each unit becomes very low.

Innovation KVIs

Impact Score: 3 The "Personal Belongings Finding" use case does not offer significant innovative value because existing devices already perform this function. However, it is the use of A-IoT technology that brings innovative value to this use case.

The integration of backscatter communication, WPT and ambient energy harvesting allows END tags to operate without batteries or external power supplies, opening the door to devices with extremely long lifespans and no maintenance. Moreover, the simplicity of END tags allows for their integration in everyday objects (clothing, accessories, keyrings, packaging...) without modifying the aesthetics or ergonomics of the product. This increases adoption and enables new products like disposable textile labels or sensors that can be inserted into single-use packaging.

Figure 4.8: Impact Scores for Personal Belongings Finding.

4.6 In-body or Wearable Medical Sensors

Table 4.15: Use Case Families for In-body or Wearable Medical Sensors use case.

Use Case Families		
Hard-to-reach devices	Massive-scale sensor networks	Extreme-lifetime applications

Table 4.16: END classes for In-body or Wearable Medical Sensors use case.

END Classes			
UP ENDs	DB ENDs	DP ENDs	CO ENDs

4.6.1 Description

In-body and wearable sensors are revolutionizing the way human activities and physiological states are monitored, expanding far beyond traditional medical applications to include wellness, sports performance, elderly care, and lifestyle optimization. These sensors function by detecting and measuring physical (e.g., motion, pressure), biochemical (e.g., glucose, hydration), or environmental (e.g., temperature, humidity) parameters through various sensing elements. Data is then processed locally or transmitted wirelessly for interpretation and action.

Wearable sensors are typically worn externally integrated into textiles, wristbands, or skin adhesives while in-body sensors are either implanted or ingested. Advances in flexible electronics, smart materials, miniaturized circuits, and wireless communication have enabled these sensors to become increasingly unobtrusive, durable, and user-friendly. For example, fitness trackers monitor cardiovascular metrics, smart fabrics detect hydration levels, smart diapers alert moisture presence [61], and implantable sensors provide real-time data for multiple medical applications (e.g. glucometers, pulse oximeters, rehabilitation feedback...).

An illustrative example involves a hybrid wearable platform combining a sole-integrated Triboelectric Nanogenerator (TENG) with a microneedle-based electrochemical sensor. The TENG, embedded in footwear, serves a dual purpose: harvesting mechanical energy from walking and acting as a gait sensor [62]. This harvested energy directly powers a low-energy microneedle sensor that continuously monitors biomarkers in interstitial fluid, creating a battery-less biochemical sensing system. Additionally, integrating lightweight AI frameworks such as TinyML enables on-device processing of gait data, facilitating real-time activity monitoring [63]. An overview of the entire system is shown in Figure 4.9.

Figure 4.9: Illustration of In-body or Wearable Medical Sensors use case.

4.6.2 Functional Requirements

Communication

Reliable data transmission is vital for wearable and in-body sensors, enabling efficient delivery of collected data to user devices or backend systems. Traditional standards like BLE remain dominant for consumer applications, offering a balance between range and power consumption, while near-field communication (NFC) supports ultra-low-power interactions, making it ideal for passive or energy-autonomous devices. In professional sports and performance monitoring, high-bandwidth standards such as UWB and emerging 5G/6G protocols enable low-latency, high-speed data streaming.

A-IoT technologies must address the trade-off between energy consumption and throughput or latency, which is critical for both wearable and in-body systems. The implementation of backscatter modulation is essential to minimize power demands, especially in energy-autonomous devices. Robust error correction mechanisms are required to ensure reliable data transmission in challenging environments, such as inside the human body. Furthermore, efficient multiple access strategies must be in place to handle simultaneous transmissions from numerous sensors and avoid signal collisions.

In-body communications often leverage body-coupled communication or near-field magnetic induction to counteract tissue signal attenuation. Hybrid communication architectures combining local edge processing with periodic cloud synchronization are increasingly common for optimizing energy consumption and preserving user privacy. Secure communication protocols are essential to ensure data integrity and protect user information.

Positioning/Location

Accurate positioning is critical for applications ranging from individual tracking to task automation. Positioning technologies range from global systems like GPS to specialized indoor localization methods. Due to the stringent power limitations of ENDS, any positioning solution must prioritize energy efficiency.

Basic context awareness, e.g., detecting walking, running, or resting, can be achieved using accelerometers, inertial measurement unit (IMU), or gait data from TENG-based sensors. Wearables may also leverage smartphone connectivity to access GPS data, while proximity-based methods like BLE signal detection provide efficient indoor localization. Geofencing can be added to trigger alerts if a user exits a predefined safe zone, enhancing safety in vulnerable populations [64].

Management

Managing networks of wearable and in-body sensors requires robust lifecycle management, including configuration, firmware updates, and secure data governance. OTA updates are essential for maintaining device security and functionality. Given the sensitive nature of the data, privacy and security must be enforced throughout the data lifecycle.

Modern platforms use AI-driven analytics for proactive maintenance, fault prediction, and contextual reconfiguration. Intelligent energy management systems are crucial to prioritise sensing and communication operations based on available harvested energy. To preserve energy, sensing and analysis modules should activate selectively, or operate based on event-driven triggers, rather than continuously. The system must dynamically adjust its sensing, processing, and transmission behaviour to optimize energy use.

Collected Information and Network Exposure

Systems should seamlessly interface with cloud platforms and edge devices via standardized APIs, supporting secure and scalable health monitoring. Data sharing must follow privacy-by-design principles, using techniques such as differential privacy and local processing to minimise exposure of raw data.

All data handling must comply with relevant regulations, including General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Strong security measures, such as encrypted communication and secure authentication protocols, are required to ensure end-to-end protection of user data.

Energy

Energy autonomy remains a central challenge, especially for in-body and lifestyle wearables. Traditional batteries often require frequent replacement, which negatively impacts both environmental sustainability and user convenience. A-IoT addresses this challenge by integrating energy harvesters into devices and efficiently storing the harvested energy in supercapacitors and small batteries.

For low-power devices like smart diapers and environmental trackers, energy-neutral operation supported by compact energy storage elements enables long-term, maintenance-free functionality. In-body sensors are also adopting WPT technologies, such as inductive coupling and

ultrasonic energy, in conjunction with energy harvesting and local energy storage, to achieve “fit-and-forget” deployment.

User-Safety and Robustness

User safety and comfort are critical for device acceptance. Materials must be soft, breathable, and biocompatible to avoid irritation or injury, particularly in long-term wear or implant scenarios. Skin-contact components, such as microneedles, must be hypoallergenic and safe for repeated use.

Devices must be mechanically robust, tolerating daily activities such as walking and exposure to moderate humidity and dust. Safety mechanisms should prevent electrical faults, overvoltage conditions, or sensor malfunctions. Secure attachment without causing discomfort is a fundamental design requirement.

AI/ML

Lightweight AI models, particularly those based on TinyML, should be employed for energy-efficient, on-device data analysis. AI processes must adapt dynamically to the energy available, delaying, simplifying, or skipping tasks as needed. Ideally, all processing should be capable of operating solely on harvested energy.

In addition to data analysis, AI/ML techniques could also be leveraged for communication-related tasks, such as filtering, interference suppression, and channel estimation, thereby improving overall system energy efficiency and performance.

Periodic retraining or updating of AI models based on collected user data can enhance personalization and detection accuracy. On-device artificial intelligence can assist in the detection of physiological anomalies, such as falls or indicators of dehydration.

4.6.3 Key Performance Indicators

Table 4.17: KPIs for In-body or Wearable Medical Sensors use case.

Device KPIs		Network KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Sensing accuracy	< 95 %	End-to-end latency	< 100 ms ; < 10 ms ¹
Device autonomy	> 30 days; > 10 y ²	Age of information	< 1 s
Avg. power consumption	< 10 μW	Packet loss rate	0.1 %
Peak power consumption	< 100 μW	Message size	< 1 kbit
		Communication range	< 1 m
		Service area dimension	2 m ²
		Max simultaneous devices	< 5 devices
		Transfer interval	Depends on magnitude
		Device speed	Static
		User-experienced data rate	100 kbps
Application KPIs		AI/ML KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Communication service availability	> 99 %	Training complexity	100 MFLOPS
Positioning/Location service availability	Not required	Inferencing accuracy	> 90 %
Positioning/Location service accuracy	N.A.	Inferencing latency	< 0.1 s
Command service availability	Not required		
AI/ML capabilities	Yes		

4.6.4 Key Value Indicators

Environmental KVs

Impact Score: 3 In-body and wearable sensors contribute to environmental sustainability by promoting remote monitoring, which reduces the need for frequent in-person visits and the associated carbon footprint from travel and facility use. Many of these devices are moving toward more eco-friendly designs, incorporating recyclable materials, energy-efficient electronics, and biodegradable components to reduce electronic waste. Furthermore, advancements in battery technology, such as energy harvesting from body heat or movement, reduce reliance on disposable batteries. By extending device lifespan through modular or upgradable designs, manufacturers help mitigate the environmental impact of frequent replacements.

Social KVs

Impact Score: 5 Wearable and in-body sensors empower individuals by providing real-time access to personalized health and performance data. They enhance quality of life by supporting aging populations, enabling inclusive participation for individuals with mobility challenges, and bridging access gaps for rural or underserved communities. The widespread adoption of these

¹ < 100 ms for non-critical alerts and > 10 ms for critical alerts.

² > 30 days for wearables; > 10 years for implants

devices also promotes a culture of self-care and proactive well-being, creating social value beyond their technical function.

Economic KVs

Impact Score: 3 Economically, these sensors offer cost-saving potential across multiple domains. For individuals, they reduce the need for frequent appointments or invasive testing by providing continuous monitoring. At a systemic level, they facilitate early detection and preventive interventions, which can significantly reduce long-term healthcare costs. Additionally, the industry around wearable and implantable sensors - from hardware manufacturing to app development - is driving job creation and innovation within the broader tech economy.

Innovation KVs

Impact Score: 4 Wearable and in-body sensors constitute a rapidly evolving area of technological innovation, characterized by the integration of microelectronics, artificial intelligence, advanced materials, and data science. Recent developments have led to increasingly sophisticated functionalities, including energy harvesting mechanisms, adaptive feedback loops, and seamless interfacing with augmented reality systems and smart environments. This interdisciplinary convergence is expanding the functional scope of such sensors, enabling novel applications beyond traditional health monitoring.

Figure 4.10: Impact Scores for In-body or Wearable Medical Sensor.

4.7 Smart Agriculture

Table 4.18: Use Case Families for Smart Agriculture use case.

Use Case Families		
Hard-to-reach devices	Massive-scale sensor networks	Extreme-lifetime applications

Table 4.19: END classes for Smart Agriculture use case.

END Classes			
UP ENDs	DB ENDs	DP ENDs	CO ENDs

4.7.1 Description

In modern agriculture, the integration of digital technologies has transformed traditional farming practices into data-driven, precision operations. However, maintaining vast sensor networks across open fields, expansive greenhouses, and remote rural environments poses significant energy and maintenance challenges. This is where ENDs present a transformative opportunity. In smart agriculture, ENDs can be deployed ubiquitously, above or under ground, to monitor critical environmental parameters like air temperature and humidity, carbon dioxide levels, light exposure, and soil conditions (e.g., temperature, pH, and moisture content), which are essential for optimal crop growth and resource usage. They can also be used to control facilities, e.g., temperature and irrigation control systems. The lightweight, maintenance-free, and ultra-low power (e.g., 1 mW) ENDs will be ideally suited for use in extensive, hard-to-reach agricultural plots where battery replacement is impractical or cost-prohibitive.

Recent 3GPP work has included smart agriculture as one of the key use cases for Ambient IoT, enabling seamless data collection via small base stations setting up pico cells or UE-based readers located in greenhouses or open fields [45]. Specifically for greenhouse case, it is mentioned that tens of thousands of sensors will need to be connected and monitored, considering greenhouse areas that reach 70,000 square meters, equivalent to ten standard football field size. For the outdoor farmland case, where it is hard to provide a stable and continuous power supply, it is mentioned that A-IoT controllers can be attached to smart agriculture equipment (e.g., irrigation or pesticide spraying gear).

From a system design perspective, the evolution toward maintenance-free agriculture enabled by ENDs supports precision farming practices [65]. This includes irrigation optimization, early disease detection, and microclimate monitoring, resulting in better crop yield, reduced water and pesticide usage, and lower operational costs. ENDs can be deployed in extremely high densities across fields and greenhouses without needing manual servicing, opening the door to granular, real-time, and large-scale agricultural analytics.

Figure 4.11: Illustration of Smart Agriculture use case.

4.7.2 Functional Requirements

Communication

ENDs must establish autonomous uplink connections and perform uplink transmission without external wake-up commands. Supported uplink transmissions can be periodic or event triggered, based on changes in environmental parameters (e.g., moisture threshold exceeded). Furthermore, ENDs must rely on ambient backscattering communication or ultra-low-power active transmission for uplink data transmission. They must support transmission of small payloads (e.g., 50–200 bits) representing sensed metrics like humidity, temperature, or CO₂ level. ENDs must also be able to interface with nearby reader nodes (e.g., a pico-cell or mobile UE) placed in greenhouses or open fields. Coexistence with thousands of similar devices operating in the same farm or greenhouse, with minimal interference and efficient channel access mechanisms, including error detection/correction, is also a very important requirement.

Positioning/Location

Systems must provide absolute position of ENDs in outdoor scenarios such as for underground soil sensing in open fields to support spatially targeted actions (e.g., precision irrigation, localized fertilization). They must also support relative positioning between ENDs in proximity for collaborative sensing or distributed decision making (e.g., pest zone detection by neighboring sensors). In indoor agriculture settings (e.g., smart greenhouses), systems must provide room- or rack-level positioning of ENDs, enabling microclimate monitoring and spatial decision support. Devices must support multi-source positioning where feasible to improve accuracy, using combinations of technologies and signals, such as cellular and global navigation satellite system (GNSS) (more applicable to outdoor fields), BLE, Wi-Fi, and received signal strength indicator (RSSI) fingerprinting (more useful to indoor greenhouses), RFID (for close-proximity sensing), and use of local references for mesh triangulation (e.g., other ENDs, static readers, base stations).

Management

Regarding management, systems must provide mechanisms for ENDs software/firmware updates, health checks to identify faults or malfunctions, and to temporarily or permanently disable ENDs, including functionality for remote deactivation (e.g., at end-of-season or for security breaches). Activation-on-demand must also be supported, allowing newly deployed or dormant ENDs to be initialized remotely by a controller or reader node.

Collected Information and Network Exposure

Systems must support access control policies for different roles (e.g., farmer, agronomist, vendor) regarding read/write permissions to specific END groups or data streams. On the other hand, ENDS must provide real-time or near real-time access to collected environmental data (e.g., temperature, soil moisture) when such data collection is meaningful to the farming task progression, as well as when energy availability and communication conditions permit. ENDS must also expose lightweight metadata (e.g., device ID, location, timestamp, sensor type) along with sensor readings to facilitate automated interpretation and integration into farm management systems.

Systems must implement Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) to ensure only authorized entities (e.g., farmer, agronomist, equipment vendor) can access END data, issue commands, or reconfigure behavior. They must also limit unnecessary exposure of metadata (e.g., device type, location, sensing role) to prevent profiling or inference attacks, especially when ENDS are deployed in sensitive agricultural zones or with proprietary crops. Security measures like data encryption at source and decryption at destination shall be used when such metadata is required, e.g., for data preparation, model feeding, training or inference purposes. In addition, systems must support policy-based retention and deletion of agricultural data, ensuring historical data is retained only as needed and deleted upon user request or END revocation.

Energy

ENDS must support multi-source energy harvesting (e.g., combining solar and RF) to improve energy availability and reliability in diverse agricultural environments. The devices must also include a small energy storage component (e.g., capacitor, micro-battery, or supercapacitor) to enable operation during temporary unavailability of ambient energy sources (e.g., night-time or cloudy conditions). The energy storage system must support safe, efficient, and rapid charging under low input power conditions (μW to mW scale). Furthermore, energy harvesting and storage systems must be robust to agricultural conditions, including moisture, dust, temperature variation, and exposure to direct sunlight or fertilizer chemicals.

User-Safety and Robustness

ENDS must operate reliably within a broad temperature range (e.g., -20°C to $+60^{\circ}\text{C}$) and high humidity (e.g., $> 90\%$), which are typical in open-field agriculture and greenhouses. In addition, internal components must be selected to prevent failure due to condensation or thermal cycling. Furthermore, ENDS must be enclosed in weather-resistant housings to withstand harsh outdoor agricultural conditions such as rain, direct sunlight, wind, humidity, frost, and dust. Systems must also include physical protection against corrosion, especially for ENDS exposed to irrigation water and soil, or to withstand disinfectants in greenhouses after crop harvest. In addition, ENDS must tolerate mechanical shocks and vibrations, including those caused by passing farm machinery, animals, or wind-blown debris, and must be UV-resistant for long-term outdoor exposure and chemically resistant to pesticides, fertilizers, and cleaning agents used in agricultural operations. Materials used in ENDS must be non-toxic and agriculturally safe, ensuring no harmful leachates enter the soil or water supply, especially for crops intended for human consumption. ENDS designed for deployment in direct contact with soil or crops must comply with environmental safety and biodegradability guidelines. Finally, manual or autonomous

fault recovery mechanisms must be in place in case of END malfunction.

AI/ML

With further advancements in energy harvesting circuits and AI-powered edge computing (e.g., TinyML), ENDs are expected to evolve into more intelligent agents capable of not just sensing but also responding to environmental changes, which are typical in outdoors agriculture environments, autonomously. AI/ML models can be applied to improve agricultural tasks (crop contamination detection, optimization of water consumption in crops watering, etc.) as well as to improve communication-related tasks (filtering, interference suppression, channel estimation, etc.). AI models must be robust to noisy sensor input and long-term drift, especially in harsh agricultural environments with variable weather, soil, and sensor aging effects. Systems should enable incremental or online learning models, allowing ENDs to adjust to seasonal changes (e.g., adapting light-harvesting prediction during cloudy months) without complete retraining.

4.7.3 Key Performance Indicators

Table 4.20: KPIs for Smart Agriculture use case.

Device KPIs		Network KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Sensing accuracy	> 95 %	End-to-end latency	< 100 ms
Device autonomy	> 10 years	Age of information	< 1 min
Avg. power consumption	< 100 μ W	Packet loss rate	< 1 %
Peak power consumption	< 1 mW	Message size	< 1000 bit
		Communication range	< 100 m; < 500 m ³
		Service area dimension	< 70000 m ²
		Max simultaneous devices	< 70000 devices
		Transfer interval	60 min
		Device speed	Static
		User-experienced data rate	1 kbps
Application KPIs		AI/ML KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Communication service availability	> 99.9 %	Training complexity	> 50 MFLOPS
Positioning/Location service availability	> 95 %	Inferencing accuracy	> 90 %
Positioning/Location service accuracy	< 1 m	Inferencing latency	< 1 s
Command service availability	> 99 %		
AI/ML capabilities	Yes		

³ < 100 m in indoor scenarios; < 500 m in outdoor scenarios.

4.7.4 Key Value Indicators

Environmental KVIs

Impact Score: 5 The Smart Agriculture use case contributes significantly to environmental sustainability by enabling precise, low-resource farming practices. ENDs reduce the need for frequent human or machinery presence in the field, minimizing fuel use and soil compaction. These devices promote resource-efficient irrigation, fertilization, and pesticide application by delivering granular, real-time environmental data. This reduces runoff and contamination of nearby ecosystems. The ENDs ambient energy harvesting nature eliminates battery-related waste and maintenance trips. Their minimal material complexity and long operational lifespan reduce life-cycle emissions and support sustainable device deployment in large-scale, remote agricultural environments.

Social KVIs

Impact Score: 4 Smart agriculture enhances food security and quality by enabling better crop management, yield optimization, and resilience to environmental variability. The use of ENDs enables data-driven farming even in rural and underserved areas where conventional IoT infrastructure may be unavailable or unreliable. Farmers benefit from improved working conditions, reduced manual monitoring, and fewer harmful exposures (e.g., to pesticides). Furthermore, the autonomy and simplicity of ENDs empower small-holder farmers, supporting inclusive technology adoption regardless of digital literacy or capital investment. Over time, these systems contribute to more equitable and sustainable food systems.

Economic KVIs

Impact Score: 4 END-based smart agriculture systems offer cost savings through reduced input waste (e.g., water, fertilizer), minimized crop loss from stress or disease, and lowered labor demands for monitoring. Their ultra-low-cost and maintenance-free operation enables massive-scale deployments even in resource-constrained settings, providing a strong return on investment over time. By enabling early anomaly detection and condition-based actions (e.g., irrigation on demand), they reduce expensive reactive interventions. ENDs also open new economic opportunities in the agri-tech market, including sensor manufacturing, data analytics, and AI-powered farm management platforms.

Innovation KVIs

Impact Score: 4 Smart agriculture with Ambient IoT introduces a high degree of innovation by combining batteryless sensing, energy harvesting, and AI-powered edge analytics for massive scale and hard-to-reach deployments. Innovations such as energy-aware sensing, TinyML-based local anomaly detection, and adaptive data prioritization enable ENDs not just to sense, but to interpret and act on agriculture-specific conditions autonomously. These advances mark a shift from conventional data collection to intelligent, sustainable, and self-managed agricultural systems.

Figure 4.12: Impact Factors for Smart Agriculture.

4.8 Asset, Product, Tool, and Item Tracking

Table 4.21: Use Case Families for Asset, Product, Tool, and Item Tracking use case.

Use Case Families		
Hard-to-reach devices	Massive-scale sensor networks	Extreme-lifetime applications

Table 4.22: END classes for Asset, Product, Tool, and Item Tracking use case.

END Classes			
UP ENDs	DB ENDs	DP ENDs	CO ENDs

4.8.1 Description

This use case focuses on providing real-time tracking of critical assets, products, tools, and individual items within confined, high-precision operational environments such as hospitals, laboratories, advanced manufacturing facilities, and pharmaceutical clean rooms. Its objective is to enable advanced process monitoring, granular quality control, robust theft prevention, and optimized operational efficiency.

Differentiating from generic end-to-end logistics, this tracking provides continuous, precise monitoring with significantly higher update rates and lower latency. It offers robust and accurate positioning, achieving sub-meter level precision even in challenging and dense indoor environments, while handling larger volumes of contextual data per item (for example, environmental conditions, usage and position history, integrity status). These capabilities enable critical applications such as process monitoring and digital twinning for workflow validation and efficiency; quality control and compliance through automated verification of item placement, position history and environmental conditions; theft control and loss prevention via real-time geofencing and anomaly detection; and operational optimization by providing insights into asset utilization and resource allocation.

In order to allow for tracking of objects, tagging is performed, similarly to current RFID scenarios. Tags have to rely on energy harvesting or ultra-low power consumption (ENDs), which is essential for the pervasive, long-term, and maintenance-free deployment required by this kind of tracking across countless items. Integration approaches include external tagging; packaging-integrated tagging (for smart consumables/kits); design-integrated tagging (for instrument/tool intelligence); and embedded item tagging (for component/product-level digital identity).

For all the objectives of this use case, precise position and continuous tracking of ENDs is crucial, requiring advanced signal processing and inference algorithms for map construction and location. A schematic overview of the use case is given in Figure 4.13.

4.8.2 Functional Requirements

Figure 4.13: Illustration of Asset, Product, Tool, and Item Tracking use case.

Communication

Passive backscatter communication is the most desirable form of wireless communications for this use case due to its support in ultra-low power ENDs [33], [66]. Active communication may be possible in future applications if receive-side power budgets are increased from the microwatt-level to the milliwatt level [27]. Nevertheless, active communication can be cost-prohibitive and energy-intensive, particularly in large or complex indoor environments. The two exemplary solutions in [33], [66] address these limitations by employing passive communication through ambient backscatter, with signal detection carried out either at the user equipment or at the network side (e.g., the APs), depending on the deployment scenario.

To enable joint backscatter communication and channel estimation (to allow for robust positioning/localization), ENDs must employ ambient backscatter communication or transmit uplink signals towards the infrastructure. For backscatter communication, the infrastructure may comprise separate transmitting and receiving APs to avoid full-duplex operation of APs. The infrastructure must detect weak and potentially heavily interfered backscatter signals from the END, where interference primarily arises from the direct transmission paths between the APs. The infrastructure must ensure high dynamic range at the receiving APs to enable reliable detection of low-power backscattered signals. The infrastructure may transmit wideband excitation signals to allow for wideband channel estimation, which is essential for ToF-based localization. The infrastructure may provide sufficient computational resources at the APs for detecting backscatter signals from the END, cancelling interference, and demodulating backscatter symbols, alongside standard processing tasks required for the legacy signals such as orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM). In multi-AP deployments, the infrastructure may maintain synchronization of time, frequency, and phase across APs to support coherent signal processing and enhance positioning accuracy and robustness. The infrastructure and the ENDs must support multiple access protocols for massive deployments of ENDs.

Positioning/Location

To enable positioning, mapping, or sensing in a broader sense, the wireless infrastructure must be capable of acquiring channel observations, i.e., noisy CSI. Several “channel parameters” can be estimated from noisy CSI and contain END-position information.

RSS-based positioning. The system in [66] is based on the use of ENDs deployed at known positions throughout the building. Each END tag periodically transmits a unique identifier by modulating and reflecting an incident RF signal, rather than actively generating its own transmissions. Two complementary configurations are considered. In the downlink-based configuration, ENDs modulate ambient cellular pilot signals (e.g., from a fourth-generation (4G) or 5G base station (BS)), and these modulations are detected by the UE through analysis of perturbations in the CSI [67]. In the uplink-based configuration, ENDs reflect the uplink signals emitted by the UE, and modulated backscatter is detected at the BS or a nearby AP [68]. In both configurations, the observed signal variations are used to determine the END with the strongest signal, whose known location serves as a proxy for the UE's position.

Angle-Delay-based positioning. The systems investigated in [69] and [70] belong to the classes of a Radio Stripes and a RadioWeaves infrastructure, respectively. We have shown in [71, Fig. 2] that in distributed MIMO (D-MIMO) infrastructures with distributed APs, angular-domain-based positioning supersedes delay domain-based positioning typically for bandwidths below 100 MHz in strong line-of-sight (LoS) channels. We found that the path overlap in strong multipath channels negatively impacts the performance in such a regime [69, Fig. 4], but large bandwidth can help resolve the multipath components. Based on measured channels, we have shown that simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) can be used to both infer the END location and a geometric map of the propagation environment, where centimeter-level positioning accuracy has been demonstrated [70].

Delay-Doppler-based positioning. Doppler-based positioning may supersede delay-based positioning in D-MIMOs infrastructures [72, p. 20]. While the accuracy of Doppler-based velocity estimation is independent of the device motion, the positioning accuracy depends on the device velocity. Nevertheless, in combination with the delay-domain, cost-effective yet accurate wireless positioning, even with a few APs is possible in realistic scenarios with harsh channel conditions such as partial obstructed-line-of-sight (OLoS) and strong multipath propagation [73]. Close to centimeter-level positioning accuracy was demonstrated on the measurements from [72]. Doppler-based or carrier-phase-based positioning [74] may be particularly suitable for localizing ENDs in backscatter communication because these channels inherently avoid the carrier-phase calibration problem.

Management

The infrastructure must provide mechanisms for the lifecycle management of ENDs. This includes discovery, identification, and logical onboarding of new ENDs into the system. Conversely, it must also support effective mechanisms for disabling and offboarding ENDs when they are no longer required or become inoperable. Furthermore, to ensure consistent and scalable deployment, the systems must facilitate centralized, automated provisioning and configuration of APs. Lastly, the infrastructure needs to offer interfaces for automated firmware updates of APs. These updates are crucial for implementing improved features, such as advanced localization and estimation algorithms, and for addressing critical security vulnerabilities.

Collected Information and Network Exposure

APs within the network are required to provide interfaces for the exchange of channel estimates or intermediate positioning/localization results. This data exchange can occur either via backhaul

links or through over-the-air interfaces. While systems may collect these channel estimates or intermediate results, the subsequent processing of this collected information can be performed either at the network edge or on centralized systems. After processing, the systems must provide the positioning/localization results to authorized entities, ensuring data access is controlled and secure.

Energy

RF WPT technology is the preferred method to power ENDs in this use case, requiring an infrastructure capable of providing efficient WPT as a service on a massive scale. Antenna arrays can provide both the transmission efficiencies required to power ENDs and the regulatory compliance to ensure exposure-safe operation [27].

User-Safety and Robustness

Robust operation even in harsh channel conditions such as low-signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and under high END mobility can, for instance, be accomplished by jointly inferring the END location and a geometric map of its propagation environment, as has been shown in [70].

AI/ML

AI and ML are crucial for enhancing the capabilities of this use case. They enable predictive maintenance by analysing usage patterns and sensor data from tools and assets, which helps anticipate potential failures, optimize maintenance schedules, and prevent downtime. These technologies also facilitate anomaly detection, identifying unusual movements, environmental deviations, or departures from standard operating procedures. This triggers immediate alerts for issues like theft attempts, quality excursions, or process errors.

Furthermore, AI and ML contribute to workflow optimization by analysing historical tracking data to pinpoint bottlenecks, streamline item flow, and enhance overall operational efficiency in complex environments. Their role extends to enhanced localization and mapping, where neural networks and data-driven approaches are expected to improve upon model-based methods, such as in hybrid factor-graph-based systems, increasing accuracy and robustness in situations where traditional models are intractable or complex. Finally, AI and ML are instrumental in automated inventory and audit, streamlining these processes by autonomously reconciling physical items with their digital twins, thereby reducing manual effort and errors.

4.8.3 Key Performance Indicators

Table 4.23: KPIs for Asset, Product, Tool, and Item Tracking.

Device KPIs		Network KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Sensing accuracy	> 95 %	End-to-end latency	< 1 s
Device autonomy	> 10 years	Age of information	< 1 s
Avg. power consumption	< 10 μ W; < 1 mW ⁴	Packet loss rate	< 1 %
Peak power consumption	< 100 μ W; < 5 mW ⁵	Message size	< 1 kbit
		Communication range	< 100 m
		Service area dimension	< 10000 m ²
		Max simultaneous devices	< 100 devices
		Transfer interval	1 s
		Device speed	< 5 m·s ⁻¹
		User-experienced data rate	10 kbps
Application KPIs		AI/ML KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Communication service availability	> 99 %	Training complexity ⁶	< 2.5 GFLOPS
Positioning/Location service availability	> 99 %	Inferencing accuracy	> 95 %
Positioning/Location service accuracy	< 1 m	Inferencing latency	< 100 ms
Command service availability	N.A.		
AI/ML capabilities	Yes		

4.8.4 Key Value Indicators

Environmental KVs

Impact Score: 3 This use case significantly contributes to environmental sustainability by enabling precise resource management and waste reduction. Through granular tracking and real-time insights, it facilitates a reduction in spoilage, particularly for perishable goods or sensitive materials in laboratories and pharmaceutical settings, thereby minimizing waste generation. The optimized utilization of assets and resources, driven by data-informed decisions, reduces overall consumption. Furthermore, the implementation of predictive maintenance, enabled by continuous monitoring of critical tools and equipment, extends asset lifecycles and reduces the need for premature replacements, leading to a decrease in manufacturing and disposal-related environmental burdens.

Social KVs

Impact Score: 3 The social impact of this ambient IoT use case is substantial, primarily through the enhancement of safety and the improvement of working conditions. For instance,

⁴ < 10 μ W for passive ENDS; < 1 mW for active ENDS

⁵ < 100 μ W for passive ENDS; < 5 mW for active ENDS

⁶ Considering fingerprinting-based positioning [75].

in healthcare environments, precise tracking of medical equipment and pharmaceuticals significantly contributes to patient safety by ensuring the right item is in the right place at the right time. For workers across all target environments, the reduction of human error, achieved through automated verification and real-time alerts, mitigates risks associated with manual processes. Moreover, optimized workflows and reduced search times for tools or assets lead to less operational stress and improved overall well-being for personnel, fostering a safer and more efficient working environment.

Economic KVs

Impact Score: 5 The economic benefits of this high-precision tracking use case are significant, leading to considerable cost savings and improved profitability. By reducing losses from misplaced items, theft, or spoilage, direct financial drains are minimized. Optimized inventory management, enabled by real-time visibility, lowers carrying costs, reduces obsolescence, and decreases the need for excess stock. Enhanced asset utilization, driven by insights into usage patterns and availability, maximizes the return on investment for critical equipment. Improved quality control, achieved through automated verification of item conditions and placement, helps reduce expenses related to rework, scrap, and product recalls. Finally, predictive maintenance capabilities help prevent expensive unplanned downtimes and extend the operational life of valuable machinery, resulting in notable savings on repairs and replacements.

Innovation KVs

Impact Score: 4 This use case represents a substantial advancement in tracking technology. It moves beyond traditional methods by offering pervasive, real-time, accurate (with sub-meter precision), and energy-efficient capabilities that are scalable. The integration of advanced AI/ML algorithms for improved localization, anomaly detection, and workflow optimization, along with the development of digital twins for physical assets, introduces a more advanced operational approach. This innovative framework allows for enhanced operational control, increased automation, and more data-driven decision-making in high-precision environments.

Figure 4.14: Asset, Product, Tool, and Item Tracking.

4.9 Museum Guide

Table 4.24: Use Case Families for Museum Guide use case.

Use Case Families		
Hard-to-reach devices	Massive-scale sensor networks	Extreme-lifetime applications

Table 4.25: END classes for Museum Guide use case.

END Classes			
UP ENDs	DB ENDs	DP ENDs	CO ENDs

4.9.1 Description

This use case explores the application of ENDs in museum environments to enhance the visitor experience through unobtrusive and context-aware information delivery. Traditional energy harvesting techniques, such as ambient light harvesting, are often infeasible in museums due to stringent conservation requirements. Many exhibits—particularly historical artifacts, paintings, and textiles—must be protected from prolonged exposure to light to prevent degradation. As a result, lighting levels in exhibition spaces are often kept deliberately low and tightly controlled, rendering light-based energy harvesting impractical or unreliable.

To address this challenge, the proposed system employs RF backscatter communication. In this architecture, END backscatter tags are deployed—preferably on the exhibit side—to serve as context beacons. These devices operate without a conventional power source, instead reflecting and modulating an incident RF signal provided by an external emitter or by the visitor’s UE. When a visitor approaches an exhibit, the associated tag is detected via proximity, enabling the delivery of multimedia or textual content relevant to that exhibit. This system design allows museums to augment the visitor experience while fully preserving the environmental conditions required for artifact protection.

The overall system concept is illustrated in Figure 4.15. The backscatter tag embeds its information into the ambient RF channel by modulating the incident signal. These modulations can be detected as perturbations in the channel estimates observed at the user equipment [67] or network-side receivers, such as indoor pico Evolved Node Bs (eNBs) [68]. Instead of using cellular signals and modems for illuminating and reading the tags, one could alternatively use Wi-Fi signals and modems. Methods for reading backscatter devices with unmodified Wi-Fi devices have been proposed in [76] and [77].

Figure 4.15: Illustration of Museum Guide use case.

4.9.2 Functional Requirements

Communication

In the context of the museum guide use case, the communication system must provide low-data-rate, ultra-low-power connectivity between passive backscatter tags and user devices. This communication should be sufficient to transmit exhibit identifiers or metadata that can trigger content retrieval on the user's device.

To ensure reliable data exchange in environments with challenging propagation conditions or congested RF channels, the communication protocols should incorporate basic error detection and synchronization mechanisms. Furthermore, the communication stack should be designed for seamless integration with COTS mobile devices and should comply with relevant IoT and wireless communication standards to ensure broad interoperability.

Positioning/Location

The system must support reliable detection of visitor proximity to individual exhibits, which is essential for enabling context-aware interactions. This functionality may be implemented by configuring thresholds based on RSS or by employing ToF estimations to determine the distance between the user device and the exhibit tag. Positioning granularity must be sufficient to associate each visitor reliably with a specific exhibit, even in closely spaced arrangements.

Management

To enable scalable deployment and context-aware operation, the system must support efficient registration and configuration of backscatter tags. The system must provide tools for registering tags, associating each with exhibit-specific metadata (e.g., exhibit identity, location, category), and configuring system behaviour in accordance with the physical layout and curatorial requirements. This includes support for batch provisioning, metadata updates, and location-aware configuration to ensure accurate and contextually relevant content delivery. In addition, the

system should support mechanisms for remote firmware updates and for deactivating or re-signing tags, thereby facilitating maintenance, content management, and adaptation to changes in exhibit arrangements.

To ensure reliable system operation and maintain a high quality of user experience, the system should implement remote monitoring and diagnostics capabilities for both individual tags and the network as a whole. These capabilities should include real-time condition monitoring, error logging, communication reliability metrics, and performance analytics. Such functionality must enable museum staff to promptly identify malfunctioning or degraded tags, thereby facilitating timely maintenance or replacement and minimizing service disruptions.

Collected Information and Network Exposure

Backscatter tags emit only static identifiers or metadata, which uniquely correspond to exhibit-specific content stored in backend systems. These transmissions do not contain any user-specific information. However, when a visitor's UE receives a packet from a tag and forwards it to the backend, the system can combine the tag data with metadata embedded in the UE transmission—such as timestamps, device identifiers, and location estimates. This composite information enables the inference of user interactions, including visit sequences, dwell times, and content access patterns. Such derived data can be leveraged for analytics, personalization, and improving the overall visitor experience.

All data processing and transmission must comply with applicable data protection regulations, including the GDPR. The collection of personally identifiable information should be minimized, and data must be anonymized or pseudonymized wherever feasible to protect user privacy. The system must support the exercise of data subject rights, such as consent management and the ability to access, rectify, or erase personal data upon request. To safeguard data integrity and confidentiality, secure communication protocols must be employed between user devices and backend systems, ensuring protection against interception, unauthorized access, or tampering.

Network interfaces, especially those accessible via user devices or cloud-based services, must be secured using strong authentication, robust access control, and end-to-end encryption mechanisms. Access to system internals, tag-to-content mappings, and visitor analytics must be strictly limited to authorized personnel to prevent unauthorized access, data leakage, and potential inference attacks.

Energy

Tags must support fully passive operation, functioning exclusively through RF backscatter modulation without any onboard energy source. This operating mode is particularly well-suited for permanent exhibitions, where long-term reliability and maintenance-free deployment are critical. By eliminating the need for batteries, passive tags reduce maintenance demands and support environmental sustainability objectives.

Conservation requirements for light-sensitive artifacts often impose strict limitations on both light intensity and spectral composition to prevent photodegradation, thereby rendering light-based energy harvesting impractical. Consequently, RF-based energy harvesting is essential to ensure reliable tag operation in these environmentally constrained settings.

For applications requiring minimal data buffering or brief periods of active computation, tags may incorporate small energy storage elements, such as capacitors. These enable short bursts of elevated activity (e.g., response timing coordination) while preserving an overall ultra-low power profile.

In short-term or temporary exhibitions, battery-assisted tags may be considered as an alternative. Although less desirable due to battery disposal concerns and their classification as hazardous waste, this approach can simplify network deployment by eliminating the dependency on reliable energy harvesting at tags. This trade-off may be acceptable in scenarios where ease of installation and operational reliability outweigh long-term sustainability concerns.

User-Safety and Robustness

The museum guide system must operate in a non-intrusive manner, avoiding the emission of light, sound, or other stimuli that could disturb the museum environment or compromise visitor comfort. All RF emissions must comply with applicable local safety regulations to ensure both regulatory conformity and a safe experience for staff and visitors.

Devices must maintain functional performance across the full range of museum environmental conditions, including low-light, variable humidity, and electromagnetic noise. In the event of tag failure or absence of interaction, default behavior (e.g., manual information access) must remain available to visitors.

AI/ML

Artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques can be applied at the receiver (user equipment or edge device) to improve the robustness and reliability of tag detection under challenging RF conditions. This includes denoising, interference mitigation, signal classification, and pattern recognition methods that enhance sensitivity and reduce false detections in multipath-rich or congested environments.

Machine learning models operating in the backend can be used to personalize content delivery based on inferred visitor preferences, prior behavior, and exhibit popularity. Such models can dynamically adapt the information presentation to improve user engagement and learning outcomes.

AI-driven analytics can analyze communication patterns and device performance indicators to detect anomalies and predict failures in tags or associated infrastructure. This enables proactive maintenance, reduces downtime, and improves system reliability, particularly in large-scale or long-duration deployments.

Aggregated visitor interaction data can be processed using machine learning algorithms to infer movement patterns, optimize spatial layout, and identify popular or underutilized exhibits. These insights can support curatorial planning, resource allocation, and crowd management strategies in real time or for long-term planning.

4.9.3 Key Performance Indicators

Table 4.26: KPIs for Museum Guide use case.

Device KPIs		Network KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Sensing accuracy	N.A.	End-to-end latency	< 2 s
Device autonomy	> 20 years	Age of information	N.A.
Avg. power consumption	< 1 μ W	Packet loss rate	< 1 %
Peak power consumption	< 50 μ W	Message size	< 96 bits
		Communication range	< 3 m
		Service area dimension	< 20000 m ²
		Max simultaneous devices	< 30000 devices
		Transfer interval	On user request
		Device speed	Static
		User-experienced data rate	50 bps
Application KPIs		AI/ML KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Communication service availability	> 99.9 %	Training complexity	N.A.
Positioning/Location service availability	> 99.9 %	Inferencing accuracy	N.A.
Positioning/Location service accuracy	< 2 m	Inferencing latency	N.A.
Command service availability	Not required		
AI/ML capabilities	Not required		

4.9.4 Key Value Indicators

Environmental KVs

Impact Score: 3 The passive, battery-free operation of backscatter tags dramatically reduces electronic and battery waste compared to conventional guided-tour devices, aligning with sustainability goals. The tags' expected >20 year lifespan further minimizes replacement cycles and associated material consumption.

By leveraging ambient RF energy from existing Wi-Fi access points or cellular signals—rather than deploying dedicated carrier generators—the system adds virtually no incremental power draw. Passive backscatter tags simply modulate reflections of signals already present, avoiding the need for extra infrastructure and minimizing lifecycle energy consumption. The elimination of batteries and the tags' multi-decade lifespan further curtail material use and waste.

However, the approach depends on the density and continuity of ambient RF coverage; in sparsely-instrumented areas or during network downtime, energy availability may fluctuate, potentially degrading tag responsiveness. Careful assessment of site-specific RF environments and, where necessary, strategic placement of supplemental emitters can mitigate these risks without undermining the overall environmental benefit.

Social KVs

Impact Score: 3 By offering an unobtrusive, context-aware guide, the system can enhance visitor engagement and accessibility—especially for users who prefer personalized, on-demand content without wearing or handling extra devices. The touchless interaction model also benefits hygiene and comfort in public spaces.

Conversely, reliance on visitors' own smartphones or dedicated RF readers may exclude those without compatible devices or with limited digital literacy, potentially widening the digital-access divide. Ensuring universal access—via loaner readers or multilingual, low-tech fallback options—will mitigate these social risks, but reduce the economical benefit.

Economic KVs

Impact Score: 3 Most contemporary museums rely on battery-powered handheld guides or badges, which incur significant ongoing costs for battery purchase, charging infrastructure, labour to swap or charge units, and eventual battery disposal. By contrast, a fully passive backscatter-based guide eliminates all battery-related expenses over its operational life. The ultra-long tag lifetime (>20 years) means virtually zero maintenance labour and no recurring consumables, delivering substantial total cost of ownership savings.

However, initial outlays for RF emitters, reader integration, and backed software may be higher than for simple battery-powered handsets. Achieving return of investment (ROI) depends on visitor volume and exhibit scale; smaller or seasonal installations might need phased deployment or shared infrastructure models to amortize capital investment effectively.

Innovation KVs

Impact Score: 4 Deploying fully passive RF backscatter for context-aware museum guides represents a novel fusion of A-IoT and cultural-heritage engagement. The approach sidesteps lighting constraints and unlocks long-term, maintenance-free installations in sensitive exhibition environments, advancing the state of the art in low-power, location-based services.

Nonetheless, the technology remains emergent: integration with unmodified COTS devices (e.g., smartphones), AI-enhanced tag detection, and scalable management tools are still maturing. Continued innovation in backscatter modulation schemes, AI/ML detection algorithms, and standardized protocols will determine how broadly this concept can be adopted.

Figure 4.16: Impact Factors for Museum Guide.

4.10 End-to-end Logistics

Table 4.27: Use Case Families for End-to-end Logistics use case.

Use Case Families		
Hard-to-reach devices	Massive-scale sensor networks	Extreme-lifetime applications

Table 4.28: END classes for End-to-end Logistics use case.

END Classes			
UP ENDs	DB ENDs	DP ENDs	CO ENDs

4.10.1 Description

Efficient logistics management is a cornerstone of modern supply chains, ensuring that goods are delivered accurately, safely, and on time. End-to-end logistics encompasses most of the lifecycle of a product—from its origin at the manufacturing site to its final delivery to the consumer. This process involves multiple stages, including production, warehousing, transportation, and distribution, each of which can benefit from intelligent monitoring and automation.

The emergence of the A-IoT has introduced a new paradigm in logistics. By embedding intelligence into everyday objects and environments, A-IoT enables seamless data collection, communication, and decision-making across the supply chain. RFID technology is a foundational element in this context. Passive RFID tags, attached to products or packaging during manufacturing, store unique identifiers and essential metadata. As goods move through the supply chain, RFID readers—strategically placed at checkpoints such as warehouses, loading docks, and retail outlets—capture data from these tags. This enables real-time tracking of product location and status. Although passive tags do not contain their own power source, they can be energized via WPT from nearby readers or mobile devices, ensuring continuous operation without the need for batteries. Beyond traditional RFID, A-IoT expands the range of capabilities. For example, temperature-sensitive goods can be monitored using semi-passive tags over a longer period of time with internal supercapacitors to expand the operation.

In addition, on-board units (OBUs) installed in delivery vehicles provide valuable telemetry data, including vehicle location, speed, fuel consumption, and maintenance status. This information supports dynamic route optimization, predictive maintenance, and improved fleet management. Together, smart tags, RFID, and other A-IoT devices form a distributed, intelligent infrastructure that enhances visibility, traceability, and efficiency across the entire logistics chain. By leveraging the capabilities of A-IoT and ENDs, businesses can achieve more resilient, adaptive, and sustainable logistics operations.

A-IoT integration into logistics workflows, in this example RFID as enabling technology, can follow several strategic approaches, each offering varying levels of traceability, durability, and cost-efficiency:

Figure 4.17: Illustration of End-to-end Logistics use case

- **External Tagging:** tags are affixed to the exterior of items, containers, or pallets. This method is widely used for inventory tracking and shipment verification due to its simplicity and low implementation cost.
- **Packaging-Integrated Tagging:** Tags are embedded directly into product packaging or a reusable transport item (RTI). This approach enhances durability and reduces the risk of tag detachment during handling and transit.
- **Design-Integrated Tagging:** tag functionality is incorporated into the product's design, often in a detachable or semi-permanent form. This strategy supports traceability throughout the product lifecycle while allowing for tag reuse or removal after sale.
- **Embedded Item Tagging:** tag components are fully integrated into the product itself during manufacturing. This method enables seamless tracking and authentication, particularly valuable for high-value goods. This tagging method can be further enhanced by combining the device function with the tag, for example, to read out diagnostic information of the device over its life cycle by the end customer.

4.10.2 Functional Requirements

Communication

RFID tags must support globally unique identification and be readable in dense tag environments, such as warehouses or shipping containers, where hundreds or thousands of tags may be present simultaneously. Bulk identification with a read accuracy exceeding 99% is essential to ensure reliability. Communication protocols must support anti-collision and error correction mechanisms, and operate across various frequency bands (e.g., ultra-high frequency (UHF), high frequency (HF)) depending on regional regulations and application needs.

Positioning/Location

While RFID passive tags do not possess active transmission capabilities, they can support positioning when deployed within a dense infrastructure of fixed reader. Same with A-IoT devices if they have no active communication capabilities. These systems estimate the position of tagged items using techniques such as signal triangulation, ToF, or RSSI. However, achieving sub-meter

accuracy with passive systems alone remains challenging and often requires environmental calibration and redundancy.

To enhance both positioning precision and contextual location awareness, hybrid systems are increasingly employed. These combine RFID with complementary technologies such as UWB for high-accuracy indoor positioning, or GPS for outdoor tracking. A-IoT devices, which often include multiple harvesting sources, sensors and connectivity modules, further enrich this ecosystem by providing continuous data streams that support real-time localization and environmental monitoring.

Management

Effective logistics management requires seamless integration of A-IoT data into resource planning and warehouse management systems. This includes real-time inventory updates, automated stock level alerts, and exception handling (e.g., damaged or missing items). Middleware must support data filtering, aggregation, and event-based triggers to reduce network load and improve responsiveness. Further, the environment, tag number and type is constantly changing. Therefore, flexible network structures must be implemented to be able to add, remove, or reconfigure new devices.

Collected Information and Network Exposure

END tags enhance logistics by monitoring environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, vibration, and shock. These parameters are essential for maintaining product quality, especially in cold chain and fragile goods transport. Collected data must be securely transmitted to cloud or edge platforms using encrypted and authenticated channels. This protects against tampering and unauthorized access, ensuring data integrity throughout the supply chain.

Energy

END tags operate without internal batteries, relying solely on harvested energy from ambient sources such as RF WPT and/or others. Energy harvesting must be sufficient to power sensing, data storage, and communication functions. RFID readers (both fixed and mobile) must ensure reliable tag activation at every stage of the logistics process, including during transit and at delivery checkpoints.

User-Safety and Robustness

The system must be robust against environmental stressors such as dust, moisture, temperature fluctuations, and electromagnetic interference. Tags and readers should comply with relevant safety standards and be designed for long-term durability, but should also consider their end of life (EoL) with option to recycle or reuse the tags. Scalability is also essential, with systems expected to handle thousands of tags simultaneously without degradation in performance. Secure digital communication of END devices in end-to-end logistics also improves user privacy. Unlike printed labels, which expose static information, encrypted transmissions allow controlled access, supporting compliance and trust.

AI/ML

AI/ML capabilities are primarily implemented on the infrastructure side (e.g., edge servers, cloud platforms) rather than on the passive RFID tags themselves. Due to their ultra-low power design, passive tags lack the computational resources for onboard processing. However, AI/ML can be used to analyse aggregated RFID data for anomaly detection, predictive maintenance, and route optimization. These insights can significantly enhance operational efficiency and decision-making across the logistics chain.

4.10.3 Key Performance Indicators

Table 4.29: KPIs for End-to-end Logistics use case.

Device KPIs		Network KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Sensing accuracy	> 95 %	End-to-end latency	< 1 s
Device autonomy	> 30 days	Age of information	< 1 s
Avg. power consumption	< 1 μ W	Packet loss rate	< 0.1 %
Peak power consumption	< 10 μ W	Message size	< 10 kbits
		Communication range	< 10 m
		Service area dimension	< 100 m ²
		Max simultaneous devices	< 1000 devices
		Transfer interval	< 1 s
		Device speed	< 5 m·s ⁻¹
		User-experienced data rate	100 kbps
Application KPIs		AI/ML KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Communication service availability	> 99 %	Training complexity	N.A.
Positioning/Location service availability	> 99 %	Inferencing accuracy	N.A.
Positioning/Location service accuracy	< 0.5 m	Inferencing latency	N.A.
Command service availability	Not required		
AI/ML capabilities	Not required		

4.10.4 Key Value Indicators

Environmental KVs

Impact Score: 3 The use of RFID technology in end-to-end logistics highly depends on the exact implementation of the technology. If normal barcode labels are replaced one-to-one with RFID tags, there will not be a huge environmental impact. But if the entire supply chain is adapted for the new technology, and recyclable RTI are implemented, or tags are directly integrated into the devices, therefore reducing the need for further package labelling, and enabling additional information throughout the lifespan of the device, environmental impacts can be substantial.

Social KVs

Impact Score: 4 By implementing RFID technology in end-to-end logistics, improvements to the efficiency and accuracy of supply chain operations can be made. This leads to faster delivery times, reduced stock-outs, and improved customer satisfaction. The real-time visibility provided by RFID technology also enhances the transparency of the supply chain, allowing consumers to track the journey of their products from the manufacturer to their doorstep. Device implemented tags further allow the end user to detect the authenticity of the device, or enable to gather more information on the device throughout its lifespan.

Economic KVs

Impact Score: 4 By reducing the need for manual inventory checks and improving the accuracy of inventory records, RFID technology helps to reduce labor costs and minimize losses due to stock discrepancies, leading to cost savings for businesses. The improved efficiency of logistics operations also leads to cost savings in transportation and warehousing, further enhancing the economic benefits of RFID technology.

Innovation KVs

Impact Score: 3 The use of RFID technology in end-to-end logistics represents a moderate innovation in supply chain management. By providing real-time visibility and accurate tracking of products, RFID technology enables businesses to optimize their logistics operations and improve overall supply chain efficiency. Mostly the innovative aspects will be present in the ability of the end user interfacing with the device tags, for example, to check authenticity, read out device information very easily, like manuals or data-sheets, or even check device status, if the tag is integrated into the device functionality.

Figure 4.18: End-to-end Logistics.

4.11 Industrial Predictive Maintenance

Table 4.30: Use Case Families for Industrial Predictive Maintenance use case.

Use Case Families		
Hard-to-reach devices	Massive-scale sensor networks	Extreme-lifetime applications

Table 4.31: END classes for Industrial Predictive Maintenance use case.

END Classes			
UP ENDs	DB ENDs	DP ENDs	CO ENDs

4.11.1 Description

Predictive maintenance supports the identification of early signs of equipment wear, reducing unplanned downtime, and maximizing service schedules. In industrial applications, energy-neutral sensing enables continuous, wireless monitoring of hard-to-reach or distributed assets without the hassle of battery maintenance.

Figure 4.19: Illustration of Predictive Maintenance use case.

Typical applications are as follows.

- **Stagnant water detection** on factory or warehouse flat roofs, where stagnant water can cause structural damage if not detected.
- **Machine hour counters**, with runtime monitoring determining maintenance planning based on actual usage instead of fixed intervals.
- **Vibration analysis** of motors, fans, or compressors, enabling early detection of misalignment, imbalance, or mechanical wear through spectral processing.
- **Thermal monitoring**, with gradual temperature drift in bearings or electrical components indicating impending faults.

These sensors often operate with periodic power supplied by harvesting sources such as vibration, indoor light, or temperature gradients. Event-driven updates and local processing reduce energy demands and enable batteryless or battery-assisted operation for years.

4.11.2 Functional Requirements

Communication

To conserve energy, devices communicate infrequently or on event detection. Low-throughput short-range wireless protocols (e.g., sub-GHz, BLE, or industrial LoRa variants) are sufficient to transmit alerts or status messages. Where backscatter or wake-up radios are used, communication is asynchronous and low-power. Gateways gather the data and forward them to the cloud or local control systems for diagnostics or visualization. The employed Medium Access Control (MAC) strategies favour energy efficiency over complexity. Simple contention-based approaches (e.g., ALOHA variants) are common but offer limited robustness, especially in dense deployments, due to their "fire-and-forget" nature and lack of collision avoidance. More reliable alternatives, such as duty-cycled time division-multiple access (TDMA), can provide predictable access with fewer collisions, but require synchronization and coordination.

Positioning/Location

Precise positioning is usually not required. The device installation is associated with specific machines or locations, and the metadata can be manually tagged during the installation. In distributed or mobile assets, the granularity to the zone or room level can be sufficient.

Management

Each sensor must have a unique ID and be associated with its intended asset in an asset management system or digital twin. Uptime, signal quality, and power availability as minimum health indicators can be checked from time to time. Devices must support fault detection and marking to allow scheduled intervention or replacement when necessary. In addition, support for OTA updates and remote parameter configuration is essential, enabling firmware updates or operational adjustments to be applied without physical access. These updates can be triggered manually by operators in response to diagnostics, or automatically pushed by cloud-based systems as part of policy-driven workflows. For example, if the cloud detects that a sensor is sending data more frequently than necessary, causing unnecessary energy drain, it can automatically issue a down-link to adjust the reporting interval or detection threshold. Beyond device-level management, the network must support effective commissioning of new devices and orderly decommissioning of obsolete or malfunctioning ones.

Collected Information and Network Exposure

The information gathered by ENDS used in industrial predictive maintenance context typically includes runtime logs such as hours active, event counts like the presence of water or vibration anomalies, and condition metrics including temperature and vibration spectrum analysis. A key challenge in this context is balancing the demand for near real-time access to data with the need to conserve device energy, as more frequent transmissions significantly increase energy consumption and thus reduce device lifetime.

Industrial telemetry is not required to be sensitive, but must be protected with encryption and secure authentication. Gateways and storage need to offer integrity, particularly in those instances where data affect maintenance choices or regulatory compliance.

Energy

Energy-neutral operation can rely on a variety of energy harvesting sources: most commonly ambient light, possibly combined with others such as vibration or thermal gradients to improve robustness by compensating for the variability of individual sources. Devices buffer harvested energy using (a combination of) energy storage elements such as supercapacitors (enabling rapid discharge for intermittent sensing, processing, and transmission tasks) and batteries (leveraging high energy density).

Event-driven architectures avoid unnecessary energy consumption. Battery-assisted nodes can be acceptable for multi-year deployment but should be avoided where replacement is not possible.

User-Safety and Robustness

Devices must be industrial-grade: resistant to extremes of dust, moisture, vibration, and temperature to ensure reliable operation under harsh conditions. They must also function reliably amid electrical noise, metallic obstructions, and harsh electromagnetic environments typical of industrial settings, where wireless communication faces reflections, interference, and signal attenuation. To prevent disruption, devices should be designed so that their operation does not interfere with the assets they monitor. The physical size of the device must be appropriate for the use case: generally less restrictive in open deployments such as rooftop monitoring but potentially critical in confined spaces such as size-constrained machinery, where compactness is necessary to avoid impeding operation or maintenance. Finally, devices should incorporate fail-safes such as watchdog timers and fallback logic to handle communication loss or internal failures gracefully.

AI/ML

Basic signal processing techniques, such as peak detection or fast Fourier transform (FFT), can typically be performed locally at the edge to pre-filter or classify data, thus reducing the volume of data that needs to be transmitted. Local ML on the sensor is constrained by energy availability, which leads to a trade-off between performing lightweight local inference with potentially lower accuracy and offloading data to cloud-based ML models, which may offer higher accuracy, but require more energy for communication. Cloud-side AI models can aggregate data across multiple assets, identify long-term trends, and provide more accurate failure forecasts.

4.11.3 Key Performance Indicators

Table 4.32: KPIs for Industrial Predictive Maintenance use case.

Device KPIs		Network KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Sensing accuracy	> 95 %	End-to-end latency	< 10 min
Device autonomy	> 10 years	Age of information	< 1 s
Avg. power consumption	< 1 mW	Packet loss rate	< 1 %
Peak power consumption	< 10 mW	Message size	< 1 kbit
		Communication range	< 100 m
		Service area dimension	< 1 km ²
		Max simultaneous devices	< 100 devices
		Transfer interval	Depends on magnitude
		Device speed	Static
		User-experienced data rate	200 kbps
Application KPIs		AI/ML KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Communication service availability	> 99.99 %	Training complexity	< 1 GFLOP
Positioning/Location service availability	Not required	Inferencing accuracy	> 95 %
Positioning/Location service accuracy	Not required	Inferencing latency	< 10 s
Command service availability	Not required		
AI/ML capabilities	Yes		

4.11.4 Key Value Indicators

Environmental KVs

Impact Score: 5 Energy-neutral predictive maintenance devices operate without disposable batteries, relying instead on energy harvesting (e.g., vibration, thermal, or solar). This design eliminates battery waste, significantly reducing the environmental footprint over the device's multi-year lifespan. With no need for frequent replacement or recharging, material usage and logistical emissions tied to maintenance are also reduced.

Furthermore, by enabling condition-based rather than schedule-based maintenance, the system can extend the life of industrial components, reduce unnecessary replacements, and lower the energy and raw material consumption associated with premature servicing.

Social KVs

Impact Score: 3 ENDs contribute indirectly to worker safety and well-being by enabling early detection of machine anomalies, reducing the risk of catastrophic failures that could cause injury or unplanned downtime. When deployed at scale, they support safer, more predictable work environments.

Economic KVIs

Impact Score: 4 The long-term cost savings of predictive maintenance are well established: reduced unplanned downtime, fewer maintenance interventions, and optimized part usage all contribute to substantial ROI. ENDS enhance this by eliminating battery-related operational costs (purchasing, charging, replacement, and disposal) and reducing the need for manual intervention.

Initial capital expenditure for energy-harvesting sensors, wireless infrastructure, and integration software may be higher than for traditional solutions, but the total cost of ownership (TCO) is significantly lower over time, especially in hard-to-reach or hazardous locations where maintenance is expensive.

Innovation KVIs

Impact Score: 4 The ability to operate without batteries in harsh or remote industrial environments is cutting-edge and opens new possibilities for “fit-and-forget” sensing systems. Innovation continues in adaptive duty cycling, federated learning, and ultra-low-power ML models.

Figure 4.20: Impact Factors for Industrial Predictive Maintenance.

4.12 Cooperative Mobile Robots

Table 4.33: Use Case Families for Cooperative Mobile Robots use case.

Use Case Families		
Hard-to-reach devices	Massive-scale sensor networks	Extreme-lifetime applications

Table 4.34: END classes for Cooperative Mobile Robots use case.

END Classes			
UP ENDs	DB ENDs	DP ENDs	CO ENDs

4.12.1 Description

Cooperative Mobile Robots will utilize numerous ENDs deployed onboard or over their operating area, to enable multimodal sensing to achieve effective collaboration and autonomous decision-making. Strategically placed ENDs of heterogeneous classes will ensure environmental awareness by feeding critical data, such as object locations, environmental conditions, infrastructure status, and system alerts to operating robots. Meanwhile, robots will supplement this information with local sensing using their cameras and other onboard sensing capabilities -both directional and isotropic-, thus ensuring situational adaptivity even in areas with limited external sensor coverage.

The integration of ENDs onboard cooperative mobile robots enables the decoupling of sensing functions from the robot’s primary power system. By leveraging energy-harvesting or wireless power transfer-enabled ENDs, sensing operations can be sustained with minimal impact on the robot’s energy budget, thereby preserving battery capacity for mission-critical tasks such as locomotion, actuation, and onboard computation. This architectural separation enhances energy efficiency and supports longer autonomous operation without compromising sensing granularity or coverage.

An exemplary setting is depicted in Figure 4.21. Some exemplary tasks that require robot coordination are the following:

- **Warehouse Inventory Management Operations:** Robots exchange localized data to streamline logistics, ensuring optimal storage and retrieval of inventory in warehouses.
- **Automated Assembly in Smart Manufacturing:** Teams of robots work in synchronized precision, dynamically adapting to assembly line demands for seamless production.
- **Autonomous Material Handling:** Multi-robot fleets optimize movement across industrial sites, reducing downtime and human intervention.
- **Infrastructure Inspection and Maintenance:** END-assisted monitoring helps robots conduct efficient structural checks and predictive maintenance without disrupting operations.
- **Disaster Response and Search-and-Rescue:** Intelligent robotic swarms coordinate in challenging environments, ensuring effective hazard detection and relief efforts.

Figure 4.21: Illustration of Cooperative Mobile Robots use case.

This seamless exchange of both raw sensory data and their insights, as obtained thanks to the use of AI/ML models onboard the robots or at the network infrastructure edge, enables robots to coordinate more effectively, adjust their movements dynamically, optimize navigation, and improve their operational efficiency. By leveraging a continuously evolving virtual model of the environment, robot operators can fine-tune task planning and execution, making autonomous systems more predictable and reliable even in complex, multi-agent scenarios. Different device types are deemed as useful in supporting this use case, ranging from cameras, temperature and humidity sensors to motion, presence and load sensors. Figure 4.21 provides some examples of device use in such a setting.

4.12.2 Functional Requirements

Communication

The network must optimize device duty cycling and wake-up signalling to ensure energy-efficient operation of ENDs while maintaining environmental perception capability, as needed for robotic task accomplishment. Reliable and low-latency communication must support continuous data exchange between cooperative robots and the network, ensuring information freshness for real-time decision making. The communication reliability that suffices to be attained for the needs of robotic task fulfilment must be underpinned by robust error detection and correction mechanisms, as well as efficient medium access control strategies tailored to such dynamic and dense IoT environments. To enable dynamic, energy-aware topology management, the network must continuously monitor IoT device power levels and support data path re-routing, preventing connectivity issues due to energy depletion. Furthermore, to maximize operational longevity and system stability, adaptive workload distribution must ensure efficient sharing of resources by ENDs. Moreover, the network must identify and recommend energy harvesting opportunities, allowing ENDs deployed on robots or at key infrastructure locations to extend operational time by leveraging available power sources in their environment.

Positioning/Location

The network must support precise and real-time positioning to enable Cooperative Mobile Robots to navigate complex environments with minimal latency. Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) technologies must provide high-resolution spatial awareness, enhancing robot perception beyond traditional localization methods. Multi-source positioning, combining radio-based sensing, END data, and onboard robotic sensors, must ensure resilience against occlusions and interference. Positioning must be both task-aware and energy-aware, adapting accuracy based on robotic goal requirements while minimizing energy consumption for prolonged operational efficiency. These capabilities will enable seamless robot collaboration and adaptive task execution in industrial and logistics environments.

Management

To enable energy-aware computing in Cooperative Mobile Robots, network management and orchestration (M&O) must intelligently allocate computing, communication and control resources, while optimizing power efficiency and operation lifetime of the END network. Given the varied energy constraints of ENDS, including backscattering and wireless power transfer, resource orchestration must prioritize low-power edge computing, ensuring that sensing and processing tasks are distributed optimally between robots, IoT nodes, and network infrastructure. By implementing adaptive workload distribution, M&O can allocate computing tasks dynamically, offloading high-energy operations to edge and cloud servers, while keeping lightweight, essential processing local to the robots. QoS-driven orchestration must further align resource allocation with mission-critical robotic operations, ensuring energy-efficient task execution without compromising system performance.

Additionally, M&O must support continuous health monitoring of ENDS, enabling proactive detection of faults, energy depletion, or degraded performance. Mechanisms for seamless device onboarding and graceful removal must be in place to maintain network stability in dynamic environments. To ensure long-term operability and security, M&O must also schedule over-the-air software and firmware updates in an energy- and task-aware manner, avoiding interference with ongoing robotic missions and minimizing downtime.

Collected Information and Network Exposure

Network exposure policies must regulate information accessibility across network operators, cloud platforms, and Operational Technology (OT) systems, ensuring that robots receive relevant sensory insights, while maintaining strict authentication and authorization controls. The network operator must oversee secure transmission of END data, such as positioning information, device identification, and environmental sensor readings, while ensuring that standardized network data (e.g., END performance feedback measurements and network analytics) remains confined to the operator's domain. In its turn, the cloud provider must manage storage and analytics access, enabling historical trend analysis and predictive modeling, while the robotic service provider must control task-specific data utilization, such as Quality-of-Experience (QoE) metrics and mission-critical sensor fusion outputs, which must not be exposed outside the application provider's control domain.

Privacy safeguards and operational transparency must be enforced through granular access management, allowing selective data sharing while protecting mission-critical robotic operations. Fur-

thermore, the network must support real-time or near-real-time access to time-sensitive data, such as robot location, obstacle detection, and cooperative task coordination metrics, based on the urgency and criticality of the robotic task at hand. For highly dynamic or safety-critical operations, low-latency data exposure and processing are essential to ensure timely decision-making and safe execution. In contrast, for less time-sensitive tasks, coarser-grained data collection and deferred processing may be sufficient, enabling more energy-efficient and scalable operation. Exposure mechanisms must be designed to balance responsiveness with security, ensuring that only authorized entities can access live or buffered data streams according to their operational role and the task's temporal requirements.

Energy

The network must support efficient energy use and sustainable power management for ENDS deployed in Cooperative Mobile Robot environments. Task-aware communication scheduling must minimize unnecessary transmissions, reducing energy consumption while ensuring mission-critical data exchange. Dynamic energy harvesting recommendations should enable devices to leverage ambient sources such as solar, kinetic, and RF-based energy to extend operational longevity. Further, simultaneous use of multiple available energy sources must be enabled to ensure robust END operation. Energy-aware resource allocation must balance workloads across IoT nodes, preventing localized depletion and sustaining continuous operation. The network must support circular energy management, ensuring efficient power use during the ML operation phase by minimizing excess consumption and enabling thermal energy recovery. END devices should integrate energy capture mechanisms, such as Seebeck effect-based thermoelectric harvesting, to reuse heat generated during ML workloads, converting it into usable power for extended operation.

User-Safety and Robustness

The network must ensure compliance with Electromagnetic Field (EMF) regulations, minimizing exposure risks for workers in environments with ENDS and robotic systems. Robotic movement safety must adhere to standards such as [78] and [79], enforcing collision avoidance, speed limits, and emergency stop mechanisms. Dynamic path planning must integrate real-time sensing and network-assisted coordination, preventing unintended interactions between robots and human operators. Fail-safe mechanisms must guarantee operational robustness, ensuring that robots can halt or reroute in case of system failures or unexpected obstacles.

In addition, ENDS must be designed to withstand harsh environmental conditions typical of industrial scenarios, including exposure to dust, humidity, temperature fluctuations, vibrations, and electromagnetic interference. This requires compliance with relevant industrial-grade protection standards to ensure reliable operation and longevity. These measures collectively enhance worker safety, system reliability, and operational continuity in demanding environments such as factories, warehouses, and logistics hubs.

AI/ML

The network should be capable to support low-power AI/ML operations, ensuring efficient model deployment and inference at ENDS, whenever this is decided. TinyML frameworks must adapt ML model size to fit varying END device classes, considering energy harvesting capabilities and available power sources to optimize ML model hosting and its training, inference, monitoring

and maintenance operations. Transfer learning techniques may be applied to enable robots and standalone ENDS to refine AI models using shared environmental context, reducing redundant retraining. Further, apart from being used for situational awareness and robot control purposes (such as manoeuvring), AI/ML models can be used to assist with communication tasks, for example, by recommending different END duty cycling or signal transmission/ reception policies for interference mitigation or avoidance. The system must also enable issuance and transfer of predicted END energy consumption along intended robot paths, leveraging real-time and historical data to optimize routing and resource allocation.

4.12.3 Key Performance Indicators

Table 4.35: KPIs for Cooperative Mobile Robots use case.

Device KPIs		Network KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Sensing accuracy	> 95 %	End-to-end latency	< 0.5 s
Device autonomy	> 10 years	Age of information	< 0.5 s
Avg. power consumption	< 1 mW	Packet loss rate	< 0.1 %
Peak power consumption	< 50 mW	Message size	< 1 kbit
		Communication range	< 20 m
		Service area dimension	< 10000 m ²
		Max simultaneous devices	< 1000 devices
		Transfer interval	On request
		Device speed	< 5 m·s ⁻¹
		User-experienced data rate	100 kbps
Application KPIs		AI/ML KPIs	
KPI	Value	KPI	Value
Communication service availability	> 99.9 %	Training complexity	< 1 GFLOP
Positioning/Location service availability	> 99 %	Inferencing accuracy	> 90 %
Positioning/Location service accuracy	< 1 m	Inferencing latency	< 10 s
Command service availability	Not required		
AI/ML capabilities	Yes		

4.12.4 Key Value Indicators

Environmental KVs

Impact Score: 3 ENDS equipped with energy harvesting and wireless power transfer can reduce reliance on conventional batteries, ensuring sustainable operations. However, robotic deployment still requires energy for communication, processing, and robot charging, contributing to environmental impact. Mitigation strategies must incorporate renewable energy sourcing, energy-efficient hardware/software design, and recyclable components, reducing lifecycle waste.

Social KVIs

Impact Score: 2 A-IoT might contribute to longer operational uptime and reduced maintenance efforts in a cooperative robotic system, which could slightly influence workforce roles (e.g., fewer tasks related to battery replacement or device monitoring). However, this feature would not significantly alter the broader social considerations, as compared to a cooperative mobile robot system incorporating conventional IoT devices.

Economic KVIs

Impact Score: 4 Unlike conventional IoT-equipped robots, END-enabled systems leverage energy harvesting WPT, thereby reducing dependency on battery replacements and lowering long-term operational costs. This shift enhances cost-effectiveness, especially for smaller businesses that may struggle with high maintenance expenses. From a market perspective, A-IoT adoption could lower entry barriers for businesses by reducing hardware costs, but it may also intensify monopolization risks if only large corporations can afford advanced A-IoT-powered robotics. In addition, regulatory frameworks must evolve to address data security, energy harvesting policies, and A-IoT-driven automation governance, ensuring fair competition and ethical deployment.

Innovation KVIs

Impact Score: 4 The thermal energy dissipated from AI/ML workload processing can be partially captured through thermoelectric harvesting and reallocated to critical robotic tasks, such as continuing model training or ensuring uninterrupted sensor data transmission, hence, reducing dependency on external power sources. Therefore, a KVI in this context would be on the “energy reuse potential” training or inference data may carry.

Also, before initiating Transfer Learning, the network must assess the usefulness of the AI/ML model in its current context, weighing this decision against an alternative decision on wirelessly transferring energy. A new KVI “AI/ML model usefulness” can be shaped to evaluate the most effective decision in space and in time.

Figure 4.22: Cooperative Mobile Robots.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

In this document, an analysis of use cases for A-IoT is conducted. Initially, A-IoT and the technologies supporting it are introduced, providing the context for understanding the rest of the document. A review of the state of the art on the use case definition for A-IoT is performed, focusing on activities carried out by SDOs and European projects. The core of the document describes several proposed use cases. These are examined through the identification of functional requirements, KPIs, and KVIs in four dimensions: environmental, social, economic, and innovative. With this approach, a view of the potential of A-IoT is provided, and insights into its practical implementation are generated. It is important to highlight that the KVI analysis performed by the experts contributing to this deliverable should be considered as preliminary, as the factors that it considers are difficult to quantify and anticipate. Further stages of this analysis and more research on END capabilities are needed to make it more accurate.

Deliverable D5.1 uses D2.1 as one of its primary references, leveraging on the classification of ENDS. Moreover, D5.1 analyses use cases that will serve as the foundation for the upcoming deliverables D5.2 and D5.3, which will develop the corresponding proofs of concept and demonstrators. D5.1 is also a reference for deliverables D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D4.1, D4.2, and D4.3, as it provides relevant KPIs and KVIs to support the development of protocols, infrastructures and algorithms to be described in those documents. D5.1 directly contributes to the achievement of Milestone 2: "*Technology trade-offs, use cases, KPIs, and KVIs defined*". Additionally, it contributes indirectly to the fulfilment of Specific Objective 4: "*Implement, test, validate, and demonstrate end-to-end intelligent END capabilities, and 6G network functionality*" by defining the use cases that will guide the development of the AMBIENT-6G's proofs of concept and demonstrators.

References

- [1] AMBIENT-6G, *D2.1 END architecture, technology trade-off, and characterization*, May 2025.
- [2] T. Pirson, L. Golard, and D. Bol, "Evaluating the (ir)relevance of IoT solutions with respect to environmental limits based on LCA and backcasting studies," in *Ninth Computing within Limits 2023*, LIMITS, Jun. 2023.
- [3] International Telecommunication Union. "Creating a circular economy for ICT equipment." (2023), [Online]. Available: <https://www.itu.int/en/mediacentre/backgrounders/Pages/e-waste.aspx> (visited on 11/24/2023).
- [4] W. Li, Q. Liu, Y. Zhang, C. Li, Z. He, W. C. H. Choy, P. J. Low, P. Sonar, and A. K. K. Kyaw, "Biodegradable Materials and Green Processing for Green Electronics," *Advanced Materials*, vol. 32, no. 33, p. 2001591, 2020. DOI: 10.1002/adma.202001591.
- [5] D. Danninger, R. Pruckner, L. Holzinger, R. Koeppel, and M. Kaltenbrunner, "MycelioTronics: Fungal mycelium skin for sustainable electronics," *Science Advances*, vol. 8, no. 45, eadd7118, 2022. DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.add7118.
- [6] A. S. Weddell, M. Magno, G. V. Merrett, D. Brunelli, B. M. Al-Hashimi, and L. Benini, "A survey of multi-source energy harvesting systems," in *2013 Design, Automation & Test in Europe Conference & Exhibition (DATE)*, 2013, pp. 905–908. DOI: 10.7873/DATE.2013.190.
- [7] H. Yang, M. Huang, M. Ren, and X. Li, "Piezoelectric energy harvesting interface circuit for small area and low power consumption, a review," *Measurement*, vol. 242, p. 116051, 2025, ISSN: 0263-2241. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2024.116051>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0263224124019365>.
- [8] S.-E. Kim, T. Kang, K.-I. Oh, M. J. Park, H.-I. Park, I. G. Lim, and J.-J. Lee, "Energy Management Integrated Circuit for Multi-Source Energy Harvesters in WBAN Applications," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 8, no. 8, 2018, ISSN: 2076-3417. DOI: 10.3390/app8081262. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/8/8/1262>.
- [9] C. Delgado, J. M. Sanz, and J. Famaey, "On the Feasibility of Battery-Less LoRaWAN Communications Using Energy Harvesting," in *2019 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM)*, 2019.
- [10] C. Delgado, J. M. Sanz, C. Blondia, and J. Famaey, "Batteryless LoRaWAN Communications Using Energy Harvesting: Modeling and Characterization," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 2694–2711, 2021.
- [11] M. Capuzzo, C. Delgado, A. K. Sultania, J. Famaey, and A. Zanella, "Enabling Green IoT: Energy-Aware Communication Protocols for Battery-less LoRaWAN Devices," in *Proceedings of the 24th International ACM Conference on Modeling, Analysis and Simulation of Wireless and Mobile Systems*, 2021, pp. 95–98.
- [12] A. K. Sultania, C. Delgado, and J. Famaey, "Enabling Low-Latency Bluetooth Low Energy on Energy Harvesting Batteryless Devices Using Wake-Up Radios," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 18, 2020.
- [13] A. K. Sultania, C. Delgado, C. Blondia, and J. Famaey, "Downlink Performance Modeling and Evaluation of Batteryless Low Power BLE Node," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 8, 2022.
- [14] A. K. Sultania and J. Famaey, "Batteryless Bluetooth Low Energy Prototype With Energy-Aware Bidirectional Communication Powered by Ambient Light," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 22, no. 7, pp. 6685–6697, 2022.
- [15] A. K. Sultania and J. Famaey, "Batteryless NB-IoT prototype for bidirectional communication powered by ambient light," *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 142, p. 103100, 2023.
- [16] L. Moons, S. Nasser, A. Sabovic, R. K. Singh, and J. Famaey, "Evaluating Fast and Grant-Free Uplink Access in Next-Generation Cellular IoT Networks," in *Proceedings of the 2024 3rd International Conference on 6G Networking (6GNet)*, IEEE, 2024, pp. 19–24. DOI: 10.1109/6GNet63182.2024.10765754. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/6GNet63182.2024.10765754>.

- [17] N. A. Mitsiou, S. A. Tegos, P. D. Diamantoulakis, P. G. Sarigiannidis, and G. K. Karagiannidis, "Proactive Scheduling for Zero-Energy Device Networks With Fast Uplink Grant," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 12, no. 7, pp. 1184–1188, 2023.
- [18] "3GPP TR 38.769 V19.0.0 Study on solutions for Ambient IoT (Internet of Things) in NR." [Online]. Available: https://www.3gpp.org/ftp/Specs/archive/38_series/38.769/38769-j00.zip.
- [19] R. Mishra and A. Mishra, "Current research on Internet of Things (IoT) security protocols: A survey," *Computers & Security*, p. 104310, 2025.
- [20] G. Callebaut, G. Leenders, J. Van Mulders, G. Ottoy, L. De Strycker, and L. Van der Perre, "The Art of Designing Remote IoT Devices—Technologies and Strategies for a Long Battery Life," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 3, Jan. 2021, ISSN: 1424-8220. DOI: 10.3390/s21030913. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/21/3/913>.
- [21] P. Miranda, M. Siekkinen, and H. Waris, "TLS and energy consumption on a mobile device: A measurement study," in *2011 IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC)*, IEEE, 2011, pp. 983–989.
- [22] K. O. Adefemi Alimi, K. Ouahada, A. M. Abu-Mahfouz, and S. Rimer, "A survey on the security of low power wide area networks: Threats, challenges, and potential solutions," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 20, p. 5800, 2020.
- [23] X. Yang, L. Shu, Y. Liu, G. P. Hancke, M. A. Ferrag, and K. Huang, "Physical security and safety of IoT equipment: A survey of recent advances and opportunities," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 18, no. 7, pp. 4319–4330, 2022.
- [24] M.-K. Oh, S. Lee, and Y. Kang, "Wi-sun device authentication using physical layer fingerprint," in *2021 International Conference on Information and Communication Technology Convergence (ICTC)*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 160–162.
- [25] F. Alwahedi, A. Aldaheri, M. A. Ferrag, A. Battah, and N. Tihanyi, "Machine learning techniques for IoT security: Current research and future vision with generative AI and large language models," *Internet of Things and Cyber-Physical Systems*, vol. 4, pp. 167–185, 2024.
- [26] J. Van Mulders, S. Boeckx, J. Cappelle, L. Van der Perre, and L. De Strycker, "UAV-based solution for extending the lifetime of IoT devices: efficiency, design and sustainability," *Frontiers in Communications and Networks*, vol. Volume 5 - 2024, 2024, ISSN: 2673-530X. DOI: 10.3389/frcom.2024.1341081.
- [27] B. J. B. Deutschmann, U. Muehlmann, A. Kaplan, G. Callebaut, T. Wilding, B. Cox, L. V. der Perre, F. Tufvesson, E. G. Larsson, and K. Witrisal, "Physically Large Apertures for Wireless Power Transfer: Performance and Regulatory Aspects," *IEEE Wireless Communications Magazine*, 2025, Accepted for publication. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.06807>.
- [28] U. Kunnath Ganesan, R. Sarvendranath, and E. G. Larsson, "BeamSync: Over-the-Air Synchronization for Distributed Massive MIMO Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 23, no. 7, pp. 6824–6837, 2024. DOI: 10.1109/TWC.2023.3335089.
- [29] B. J. B. Deutschmann and P. Vouras, *Spatiotemporal Synchronization of Distributed Arrays using Particle-Based Loopy Belief Propagation*, 2025. arXiv: 2504.00744 [eess.SP]. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.00744>.
- [30] K. Wu, J. A. Zhang, X. Huang, R. W. Heath, and Y. J. Guo, "Green Joint Communications and Sensing Employing Analog Multi-Beam Antenna Arrays," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 61, no. 7, pp. 172–178, 2023. DOI: 10.1109/MCOM.007.2200495.
- [31] A. Azarbahram, O. L. A. López, and M. Latva-Aho, "Waveform Optimization and Beam Focusing for Near-Field Wireless Power Transfer With Dynamic Metasurface Antennas and Non-Linear Energy Harvesters," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 1031–1045, 2025. DOI: 10.1109/TWC.2024.3503908.
- [32] V. Jamali, A. M. Tulino, G. Fischer, R. R. Müller, and R. Schober, "Intelligent Surface-Aided Transmitter Architectures for Millimeter-Wave Ultra Massive MIMO Systems," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 2, pp. 144–167, 2021. DOI: 10.1109/OJCOMS.2020.3048063.
- [33] L. D'Angelo, B. J. Deutschmann, and K. Witrisal, "Combined Wideband Channel Estimation and Direct Link Interference Mitigation in Bistatic Backscatter Systems," in *2024 IEEE 25th International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC)*, 2024, pp. 506–510. DOI: 10.1109/SPAWC60668.2024.10694033.
- [34] A. Kaplan, J. Vieira, and E. G. Larsson, "Direct Link Interference Suppression for Bistatic Backscatter Communication in Distributed MIMO," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 1024–1036, 2024.

- [35] O. L. A. López, H. Alves, R. D. Souza, and S. Montejo-Sánchez, "Statistical Analysis of Multiple Antenna Strategies for Wireless Energy Transfer," vol. 67, no. 10, pp. 7245–7262, 2019. DOI: 10.1109/TCOMM.2019.2928542.
- [36] R. M. Dreifuerst and R. W. Heath, "Massive MIMO in 5G: How Beamforming, Codebooks, and Feedback Enable Larger Arrays," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 61, no. 12, pp. 18–23, 2023. DOI: 10.1109/MCOM.001.2300064.
- [37] B. J. B. Deutschmann, T. Wilding, M. Graber, and K. Witrissal, "XL-MIMO Channel Modeling and Prediction for Wireless Power Transfer," in *2023 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC Workshops)*, 2023, pp. 1355–1361. DOI: 10.1109/ICCWorkshops57953.2023.10283480.
- [38] TensorFlow, *TensorFlow Lite for Microcontrollers*, <https://www.tensorflow.org/lite/microcontrollers>, 2024.
- [39] Arm Ltd., *CMSIS-NN: Efficient Neural Network Kernels for Arm Cortex-M CPUs*, <https://developer.arm.com/solutions/machine-learning-on-arm/developer-material/how-to-guides/cmsis-nn>, 2024.
- [40] A. Adi *et al.*, "Energy-Aware Machine Learning for IoT Devices: A Survey," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2309.00022>.
- [41] A. Dhar *et al.*, "On-Device Machine Learning: A Survey from the Algorithmic and Learning Theory Perspective," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2301.12345*, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.12345>.
- [42] Y. Zhang *et al.*, "Tiny Continual Learning on Energy-Harvesting Devices," *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 1–25, 2022.
- [43] B. Sudharsan, J. G. Breslin, M. Tahir, M. Intizar Ali, O. Rana, S. Dustdar, and R. Ranjan, "OTA-TinyML: Over the Air Deployment of TinyML Models and Execution on IoT Devices," *en, IEEE Internet Computing*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 69–78, May 2022, ISSN: 1089-7801, 1941-0131. DOI: 10.1109/MIC.2021.3133552. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9811289/>.
- [44] 3GPP, *Specification # 38.848; Study on Ambient IoT (Internet of Things) in RAN; Release 18*, Sep. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=4146>.
- [45] 3GPP, *Specification # 22.840; Study on Ambient power-enabled Internet of Things*, Dec. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=4045>.
- [46] 3GPP, *Specification # 22.369; Service requirements for Ambient power-enabled IoT*, Sep. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=4232>.
- [47] IEEE, *IEEE 802.11-23/0436r0; Technical Report on support of AMP IoT devices in WLAN*, Mar. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://mentor.ieee.org/802.11/dcn/23/11-23-0436-00-0amp-technical-report-on-support-of-amp-iot-devices-in-wlan.docx>.
- [48] ADROIT6G, *D2.1 Requirements, use cases and system architecture – Initial*, Jul. 2023. [Online]. Available: https://adroit6g.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/ADROIT6G_D2.1_Requirements-Use-cases-Architecture_Final.pdf.
- [49] ADROIT6G, *D2.3 Requirements, use cases and system architecture*, Jan. 2024. [Online]. Available: https://adroit6g.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/ADROIT6G_D2.3_Final.pdf.
- [50] HEXA-X, *Deliverable D1.1 6G Vision, use cases and key societal values*, Feb. 2021. [Online]. Available: https://hexa-x.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Hexa-X_D1.1.pdf.
- [51] HEXA-X-II, *Deliverable D1.2 6G Use Cases and Requirements*, Dec. 2023. [Online]. Available: https://hexa-x-ii.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Hexa-X-II_D1.2.pdf.
- [52] IntelloT, *Deliverable D2.1 Use case specification & Open Call definition (first version)*, Mar. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://intelliot.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Deliverable-D2.1-Use-case-specification-and-Open-Call-definition-1.pdf>.
- [53] IntelloT, *Deliverable D2.4 Use Case specification & Open Call definition (final version)*, Apr. 2022. [Online]. Available: https://intelliot.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/IntelloIoT_deliverable_D2.4.pdf.
- [54] REINDEER, *D1.1. Use case-driven specifications and technical requirements and initial channel model*, Oct. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/5561844>.
- [55] SUPERIOR, *D1.4 Description of selected scenarios, applications, and their requirements (2)*, Dec. 2024.
- [56] "How the Bluetooth® Electronic Shelf Label Standard Will Impact the Smart Retail Market," ABI Research, Tech. Rep., Jun. 2023.

- [57] J.-S. Park and B.-J. Jang, "Electronic shelf label system employing a visible light identification link," in *2016 IEEE Radio and Wireless Symposium (RWS)*, 2016, pp. 219–222.
- [58] E. E. Dikel, Y. E. Li, M. Vuotari, and S. Mancini, "Evaluating the standby power consumption of smart LED bulbs," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 186, pp. 71–79, 2019, ISSN: 0378-7788. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2019.01.019>.
- [59] J. Cappelle, L. V. der Perre, E. Fitzgerald, S. Ravyts, W. Gajda, V. D. Smedt, B. Cox, and G. Callebaut, *IoT on the Road to Sustainability: Vehicle or Bandit?* 2024. arXiv: 2405.20706 [eess.SP]. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.20706>.
- [60] B. Aliakbarian, S. Ghirlandi, A. Rizzi, R. Stefanini, and G. Vignali, "Life cycle assessment of plastic and paper-based ultra high frequency RFID tags," *International Journal of RF Technologies*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 17–32, Jun. 2024. DOI: 10.3233/RFT-230044.
- [61] J. Sennesael, A. Moerman, H. Rogier, and P. Van Torre, "Carbon-Ink Sensing Patterns for a Contactless Smart Diaper System," in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Flexible and Printable Sensors and Systems (FLEPS)*, 2024, pp. 1–4. DOI: 10.1109/FLEPS61194.2024.10603972.
- [62] J. Li, Z. Xie, Z. Wang, Z. Lin, C. Lu, Z. Zhao, Y. Jin, J. Yin, S. Mu, C. Zhang, W. Gui, X. Liang, J. Wang, and W. Ding, "A triboelectric gait sensor system for human activity recognition and user identification," *Nano Energy*, vol. 112, p. 108473, 2023, ISSN: 2211-2855. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2023.108473>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2211285523003105>.
- [63] H. Hassan, M. Abdullah, M. Z. Hussain, M. Zulkifl Hasan, M. Mustafa, A. Khalid, R. Awan, U. Hussain, Z. A. Khan, and A. Javaid, "TinyML-Based Gait Recognition for User Detection on an STM32L4 IoT Node," in *2024 IEEE 9th International Conference for Convergence in Technology (I2CT)*, 2024, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/I2CT61223.2024.10543752.
- [64] W. Chantaweesomboon, "Bluetooth Geo-Fence for Elderly and Patient Care," in *2021 25th International Computer Science and Engineering Conference (ICSEC)*, 2021, pp. 252–255. DOI: 10.1109/ICSEC53205.2021.9684648.
- [65] A. N. Arun, B. Lee, F. A. Castiblanco, D. R. Buckmaster, C.-C. Wang, D. J. Love, J. V. Krogmeier, M. M. Butt, and A. Ghosh, "Ambient IoT: Communications Enabling Precision Agriculture," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 137–143, 2025. DOI: 10.1109/MCOM.003.2400508.
- [66] S. Yang, Y. Bénédict, D.-T. Phan-Huy, J.-M. Gorce, and G. Villemaud, "Indoor Localization of Smartphones Thanks to Zero-Energy-Devices Beacons," in *2024 18th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, 2024, pp. 1–5. DOI: 10.23919/EuCAP60739.2024.10501308.
- [67] J. Liao, X. Wang, K. Ruttik, R. Jäntti, and D.-T. Phan-Huy, "In-Band Ambient FSK Backscatter Communications Leveraging LTE Cell-Specific Reference Signals," *IEEE Journal of Radio Frequency Identification*, vol. 7, pp. 267–277, 2023. DOI: 10.1109/JRFID.2023.3280108.
- [68] J. Liao, T. Zhang, K. Ruttik, R. Jäntti, and D.-T. Phan-Huy, "Ambient Backscatter Communication in LTE Uplink Sounding Reference Signal," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.10952*, 2025.
- [69] A. Fascista, B. J. B. Deutschmann, M. F. Keskin, T. Wilding, A. Coluccia, K. Witrals, E. Leitinger, G. Seco-Granados, and H. Wymeersch, "Joint Localization, Synchronization and Mapping via Phase-Coherent Distributed Arrays," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 412–429, 2025. DOI: 10.1109/JSTSP.2025.3533111.
- [70] B. J. B. Deutschmann, E. Leitinger, and K. Witrals, *Geometry-Based Channel Estimation, Prediction, and Fusion*, 2025. arXiv: 2503.17868 [eess.SP]. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.17868>.
- [71] A. Fascista, B. J. B. Deutschmann, M. F. Keskin, T. Wilding, A. Coluccia, K. Witrals, E. Leitinger, G. Seco-Granados, and H. Wymeersch, "Uplink Joint Positioning and Synchronization in Cell-Free Deployments with Radio Stripes," in *2023 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC Workshops)*, 2023, pp. 1330–1336. DOI: 10.1109/ICCWorkshops57953.2023.10283650.
- [72] C. Nelson, X. Li, A. Fedorov, B. Deutschmann, and F. Tufvesson, "Distributed MIMO Measurements for Integrated Communication and Sensing in an Industrial Environment," *Sensors*, vol. 24, no. 5, 2024, ISSN: 1424-8220. DOI: 10.3390/s24051385. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/24/5/1385>.
- [73] B. Deutschmann, C. Nelson, M. Henriksson, G. Marti, A. Kosasih, N. Tervo, E. Leitinger, and F. Tufvesson, "Accurate Direct Positioning in Distributed MIMO Using Delay-Doppler Channel Measurements," in *2024 IEEE 25th International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC)*, 2024, pp. 606–610. DOI: 10.1109/SPAWC60668.2024.10694279.

- [74] L. Görtzschacher, J. Grosinger, H. N. Khan, and W. Bösch, "Fast two dimensional position update system for UHF RFID tag tracking," in *2017 IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium (IMS)*, 2017, pp. 1331–1334. DOI: [10.1109/MWSYM.2017.8058857](https://doi.org/10.1109/MWSYM.2017.8058857).
- [75] A. Pirnat, B. Bertalančič, G. Cerar, M. Mohorčič, M. Meža, and C. Fortuna, "Towards Sustainable Deep Learning for Wireless Fingerprinting Localization," in *ICC 2022 - IEEE International Conference on Communications*, 2022, pp. 3208–3213. DOI: [10.1109/ICC45855.2022.9838464](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICC45855.2022.9838464).
- [76] A. Abedi, M. H. Mazaheri, O. Abari, and T. Brecht, "Witag: Rethinking backscatter communication for wifi networks," in *Proceedings of the 17th ACM workshop on hot topics in networks*, 2018, pp. 148–154.
- [77] E. Soltanaghaei, A. Dongare, A. Prabhakara, S. Kumar, A. Rowe, and K. Whitehouse, "Tagfi: Locating ultra-low power wifi tags using unmodified wifi infrastructure," *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1–29, 2021.
- [78] I. O. for Standardization, *Robots and robotic devices — Safety requirements for industrial robots — Part 1: Robots*, 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/51330.html>.
- [79] R. I. Association and A. N. S. Institute, *Industrial Robots and Robot Systems — Safety Requirements*, 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://webstore.ansi.org/standards/ria/ansiriar15062012>.